

Review

Continuous fiber cellular structures: a state-of-the-art review on structural design, optimization, applications and future challenges

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ABSTRACT

Continuous Fiber Cellular Structures (CFCs) represent a significant advancement in material science and engineering, characterized by their lightweight configurations and tailorable properties. These structures are increasingly leveraged across various industries, including aerospace, automotive, and biomedical sectors, owing to their superior mechanical properties, such as high strength-to-weight ratios and exceptional energy absorption capabilities. However, issues such as the manufacturing complexity, cost-effectiveness, and durability of these structures under varying environmental conditions continue to pose significant challenges. Furthermore, the integration of CFCs into existing manufacturing processes demands innovative solutions to overcome the technological limitations associated with their production and application. This review provides a comprehensive insight into the current state of continuous fiber cellular structures, focusing on the structural design methodologies and optimizations that underpin their development, their applications across different industries, and the technological challenges that must be addressed to realize their potential fully. This paper also identifies the core directions for guiding the future development of CFCs technology, offering novel perspectives and transformative ideas to drive the continued advancement of the field.

Abbreviation

2D	Two-Dimensional
3D	Three-Dimensional
4D	Four-Dimensional
AI	Artificial Intelligence
CCF	Continuous Carbon Fiber
CCS	Cellular Composite Structure
CFR	Carbon-Fiber-Reinforced
CFRP	Carbon-Fiber-Reinforced Polymer
CFCS	Continuous Fiber Cellular Structure
CFRTPC	Continuous Fiber-Reinforced Thermoplastic Composite
FDM	Fused-Deposition Modelling
FEA	Finite-Element Analysis
FFF	Fused-Filament Fabrication
GFR	Glass-Fiber-Reinforced
KFR	Kevlar-Fiber-Reinforced
MBB	Messerschmitt-Bölkow-Blohm

PA	Polyamide
PLA	Polylactic Acid
SIMP	Solid Isotropic Material with Penalization
TPU	Thermoplastic Polyurethane

1. Introduction

Since the early 2000s, cellular structures fabricated from continuous fibers have transitioned from conceptual studies to critical components in high-performance engineering, owing to their exceptional combination of low weight, tunable mechanical properties, and thermal stability [1–5]. In aerospace, initial implementations focused on lightweight panels, leading edges, and structural frames. This was done with respect to applications demanding high strength-to-weight ratios, superior energy absorption, and fatigue resistance [6]. The advent of advanced additive manufacturing platforms around 2008 further expanded the design envelope, enabling geometrically complex lattices that maximized weight savings without compromising performance [7].

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By the early 2010s, the automotive sector adopted Continuous Fiber Cellular Structures (CFCs) for crash-resistant vehicle frames and under-the-hood components such as engine mounts and suspension links, realizing reductions in vehicle mass [8], fuel consumption, and emissions [9]. Parallel studies on the crashworthiness of thin-walled and filament-wound composite tubes have demonstrated the remarkable energy absorption capabilities of hybrid and thermoplastic fiber-reinforced systems [10,11], as well as enhanced lateral crushing resistance of aluminum–polymer composite shells under impact loading [12]. These findings further underscore the relevance of fiber-dominated cellular composites for energy-dissipative and safety-critical applications. Concurrently, biomedical researchers harnessed CFCs to create fiber-reinforced scaffolds and patient-specific implants that closely mimic the hierarchical structure and mechanical behavior of natural bone, thereby alleviating stress-shielding and biocompatibility concerns [13,14] associated with metallic implants [15]. More recently, CFCs have made inroads into marine and civil engineering. Their corrosion resistance and high specific strength have driven the design of lightweight, durable hulls and superstructures for ships and underwater vehicles [16], as well as flexible, high-strength bridge components and reinforcement systems that minimize material usage and maintenance demands [17] (Fig. 1).

1.1. Bibliometric perspectives

1.1.1. Functional structure and printing path design of CFCs

Over the past decade (2015–2025), three interrelated research themes have driven the evolution of CFCs: (1) mechanical response and energy-absorption performance, (2) Three-Dimensional (3D)-printing path design, and (3) shape-memory architectures. Impact-energy dissipation is governed primarily by the underlying lattice topology and material distribution, while the trajectory of the print head controls internal stress fields and interlayer cohesion. Architected lattices incorporating thermally or mechanically activated fibers can, in turn, be programmed to deform and recover on demand. Together, these

capabilities underpin next-generation lightweight systems with enhanced resilience and adaptability (Fig. 2).

Initially focused on quantifying basic elastic properties, CFCs have subsequently shifted since 2018 toward optimizing energy absorption [18]. This prompted the development of various design strategies, including functionally graded [19–21], bi-material, bio-inspired [22–24], and hierarchical structures [25–27]. A surge in related publications since 2019 highlights significant academic and industrial interest in CFCs for developing crashworthy and impact-mitigating components. Experimental studies traced premature failures at ligament joints to stress concentrations at fiber-matrix interfaces and print-path intersections. In response, optimized print-path strategies were developed to reinforce these weak points, with related publications surging since 2019 (Fig. 2b), indicating a focus on linking process to performance. Additionally, to create reusable and adaptive structures, shape-memory functionality has been integrated via 4D printing, using stimuli-responsive materials to form programmable lattices capable of repeated deformation-recovery cycles. This theme exhibited the fastest publication growth from 2023 to 2024 (Fig. 2c), highlighting the rising demand for time-dependent, cyclic performance in applications from aerospace components to self-healing gear.

1.1.2. Structural and material optimization of CFCs

Topology-optimization studies of cellular lattices emerged in 2015, peaking at 41 publications in 2024 before a slight decline (Fig. 3a). Research on fiber-orientation optimization remained limited until 2020 but then surged to 19 papers in 2024 (Fig. 3b). Multiscale concurrent optimization, which unifies these approaches, appeared around 2018 and peaked at 11 publications in 2021 and 2023 (Fig. 3c). These fields are primarily driven by engineering and materials science, with significant contributions from computer science, mathematics, and physics (Fig. 3d–f).

Driven by advances in computation, additive manufacturing, and collaboration, lattice design has evolved from empirical approaches to integrated multiscale optimization (Figs. 2 and 3). Key challenges

Fig. 1. Potential applications of cellular structures fabricated by continuous fibers.

Fig. 2. Publication trends and subject distribution of two-dimensional (2D) and 3D CFCs research (2015–2025): (a, d) Mechanical response and energy absorption; (b, e) 3D printing path design; (c, f) Shape memory structures.

Fig. 3. Publication trends and subject distribution of CFCs optimization research (2015–2025): (a, d) cellular structures optimization; (b, e) fiber-orientation optimization; (c, f) multiscale optimization.

include incorporating manufacturability constraints, reducing computational costs, and bridging the numerical-experimental gap. Machine-learning techniques are emerging as a promising solution to accelerate convergence and expand design-space exploration, paving the way for multifunctional cellular composites [28].

Despite numerous surveys on cellular materials [3,5,6,17,29,30], a

critical void persists in the literature. To date, no review has simultaneously integrated a) structural classifications, b) design methodologies, and c) performance characterizations of continuous-fiber cellular lattices within a single, coherent framework. This identified research gap underscores the lack of a unified, fiber-centric roadmap that connects topological design to manufacturing and application. The primary

objective of this review is to bridge this gap by providing the first comprehensive synthesis dedicated to CFCS establishing a definitive roadmap for their advancement. In response, this article offers the first truly fiber-centric synthesis, establishing a definitive roadmap for the advancement of CFCS technology. **The novelty of this review is therefore anchored in three key pillars:**

1. **A Novel and Unified Taxonomy:** We introduce a structured classification of CFCS based on spatial configuration (2D vs. 3D) and Poisson's ratio, accompanied by comprehensive meta-analyses (Tables 2 and 3) that directly link topological architecture to mechanical performance, providing a clear design selection guide.
2. **A Clarified Design Paradigm:** We explicitly separate *structural design* (defining the admissible space) from *optimization* (searching within that space), a distinction that clarifies the core design considerations and enables more effective mix-and-match strategies for future research (Section 3).
3. **A Forward-Looking Synthesis:** We provide a critical synthesis not only of current-state modeling, manufacturing, and optimization challenges (Table 7) but also of transformative future directions, including the integration of quantum materials, Artificial Intelligence (AI)-driven design, and advanced sustainability metrics (Section 5), offering a perspective that guides the field beyond incremental advancements.

The logical flow of this review is structured as follows: Section 2 establishes a novel taxonomy of 2D and 3D topologies, including a meta-analysis of how each lattice architecture governs key mechanical behaviors. Building upon this structural foundation, Section 3 delineates the core design considerations, separating structural design principles from optimization techniques to clarify the admissible design space and the methods for navigating it. This section critically examines state-of-the-art modelling and optimization strategies for tailoring these structures to achieve targeted mechanical objectives. Subsequently, Section 4 synthesizes the prevailing challenges and limitations across modeling, manufacturing, and optimization domains. Finally, Section 5 concludes the review by summarizing the key findings and proposing transformative directions and key application areas for future investigation. By unifying structural, design, performance, and forward-looking perspectives, this review provides a comprehensive guide for the development and deployment of next-generation continuous-fiber cellular systems.

2. Taxonomy & design drivers

2.1. Enhancements in mechanical properties of cellular structures with fiber-reinforcement

The extraordinary load-bearing capabilities of CFCSs derive from the synergy between tailored lattice geometries and uninterrupted fiber continuity, yielding order-of-magnitude improvements in strength, stiffness, toughness, and energy dissipation [30–37]. Not only the embedding reinforcing fibers, but also the orientation of them can have a great impact on mechanical properties and behaviors of cellular structures. Dong et al. [38] reported that designing appropriate printing paths enhances the resulting mechanical properties of the continuous fiber reinforced cellular structural composites. For instance, the orientation of fibers in a stretching direction intensifies the tensile strength of the cellular structure. Giarmas et al. [39] addressed the effects of fiber orientation on the mechanical properties of 3D Printed continuous glass fiber reinforced nylon cellular structures. They strengthened hexagonal unit cells with glass fibers at three orientation angles of 0°, 45° and 90° and two different fiber infill patterns including a concentric fill and isotropic fiber fill pattern. The concentric fill prevented the cellular structure from bending along out-of-plane axes and the wall from deformation. The other infill pattern, i.e., an isotropic fiber fill pattern

intensified the bending resistance of the cellular structure in the in-plane direction. This pattern can transform any bending loading into tensile loads which are tolerated by the fibers, without difficulty. Kepenekci et al. [40] addressed the impact of fiber-reinforcement and raster orientation on the tensile and compression mechanical properties of solid and cellular 3D printed structures made of polyamide. Examining 0° (parallel), 90° and 0° (concentric) raster orientations. Tensile samples with 90° raster orientation did not exhibit any apparent plastic deformation. Besides, both fiber-reinforcement and raster orientation altered the mechanical properties, significantly. In particular, the tensile stiffness and strength had their best values for 0° (concentric) samples. However, fiber-reinforcement had an unfavorable effect on the strain at fracture. Synergetic effects of longitudinal and radial fiber-reinforcement studied by Szederkenyi et al. [41]. Employing radially Carbon-Fiber-Reinforced Polymer (CFRP) shells with fiber-reinforced triply periodic minimal surface, an enhanced energy absorption behavior with quasi-stable failure was captured. It was also concluded that the effects of fiber-reinforcement on the specific energy absorption of the cellular structure were orientation-dependent. Where, the cellular structures with Z-oriented layers of printing exhibited lower energy absorption capacity than those with XY-oriented layers of material. Chen et al. [42] introduced a novel 3D printing technique to fabricate in-plane and through-plane fiber-reinforced lattice structures. They reported that traditional method of fiber-reinforcement within the plane of material deposition during 3D printing has restricted the ability to obtain substantial improvements in mechanical properties. Using an embedded 3D printing approach, they gained full control over fiber alignment in 3D space, i.e., in-plane and through-plane directions. Both mechanical properties and thermal conductivity were enhanced sharply by employing this novel 3D printing method. Furthermore, programmable anisotropy ratio and directional elastic stiffnesses will be obtainable for applications such as morphing cellular structures and functionally graded lattices. In the following subsections, we examine how embedding continuous fibers alters mechanical behavior under primary loading modes.

2.1.1. Tensile and flexural behaviors

Early reinforcement strategies, such as incorporating discontinuous fillers into thermoplastic feedstock; yielded modest gains due to uneven fiber distribution and poor orientation control [30,43–45]. The advent of co-extrusion Fused-Deposition Modelling (FDM), which simultaneously feeds continuous-fiber and polymer filaments, overcame these limitations by enabling precise fiber placement and alignment within each printed layer (Fig. 4a) [30,38,46–50]. The inclusion of shape-memory polymers as the matrix further expands design flexibility, allowing stiffness and toughness to be tuned in response to thermal or mechanical stimuli [36,51].

Under uniaxial tension, fibers concentrated at the lattice core (Fig. 4a) bear the majority of applied loads, delaying matrix yielding and substantially increasing fracture resistance [38,53,54]. Systematic studies reveal that a mere 3.8 % increase in fiber content can raise ultimate tensile strength by over 300 % relative to unreinforced lattices [53]. Fiber orientation, controlled via cell topology and ligament direction, is equally critical. Aligning fibers parallel to the principal load vector maximizes stress transfer and tensile stiffness [38,47,49,53,54]. Flexural performance likewise benefits from CFR [55]. When fibers are oriented along expected bending axes, lattices exhibit significantly higher flexural rigidity and load capacity [30,46,56,57]. In comparative tests of sandwich panels, substituting polyethylene-terephthalate cores with carbon-fiber-reinforced lattices yielded improvements in energy-absorption capacity, flexural-rigidity-to-weight, and peak load bearing by factors of 8.6, 4.1, and 2.6, respectively [46]. The influence of unit-cell dimensions on fiber distribution and mechanical response is illustrated in Fig. 4b [38,53]. Processing parameters further modulate tensile and flexural outcomes [58]. Layer thickness dictates the number of fiber-rich passes. Thinner layers increase overall fiber volume and

Fig. 4. (a) Mechanical role of fiber reinforcement in matrix [52]. (b) Influence of fiber location and unit cell dimensions [38,53]. (c) Carbon-Fiber-Reinforced (CFR) structure in resisting compression buckling [33]. (d) Compressive deformation of a CFR lattice [47]. (e) Comparative deformation of auxetic metamaterial with and without CFR [47]. (f) Manufacturing defects in 3D-printed re-entrant lattice [47].

tensile strength at the expense of longer build times [38,49,53,54]. Print speed and raster spacing control void formation and fiber continuity. Excessive speeds risk fiber breakage and voids that weaken interlayer bonds, whereas slower deposition fosters uniform polymer flow and intact fibers [59]. Optimal interlayer overlap, as governed by print spacing and layer height, minimizes voids and enhances fiber-matrix adhesion, as evidenced by the defect patterns shown in Fig. 4f [52, 59–62]. Voids act as crack-initiation sites, promoting delamination and fiber pull-out under axial and bending loads [38,47,49,53,54,56,59].

2.1.2. Compressive behavior

Under compression, CFR lattices display markedly different failure mechanisms and substantially higher load-bearing capacity than pure-polymer structures [63]. Reinforced configurations have demonstrated up to 224 % increases in peak compressive strength [32]. The presence of continuous fibers alters buckling behavior. Rather than uniform Euler buckling, ligaments undergo irregular deformation that engages multiple struts in load sharing (Fig. 4c) [33]. Unreinforced lattices typically fail by elastic buckling followed by plastic collapse and ligament fracture (Fig. 4d) [32]. Auxetic composite architectures, by contrast, permit ligament rotation that reduces effective Poisson's ratio and delays buckling; embedded fibers further strengthen ligament walls, inhibiting crack nucleation and local instability (Fig. 4e) [47]. Moreover, continuous fibers extend the post-buckling plateau by arresting crack propagation within ligaments, enabling higher ultimate strains and specific energy absorption. Glass-fiber-reinforced lattices have exhibited an 86.3 % increase in compressive stiffness [64] and a 100 % gain in energy absorption with only a 6 % mass penalty [47]. Integration of shape-memory polymers amplifies cyclic energy dissipation and recoverability. The associated CFR lattices consistently outperform unreinforced counterparts in energy absorption over successive cycles [60], and Shape-Memory Polymer-reinforced auxetic lattices maintain over 90 % shape recovery after six compression cycles [61].

Recently, the application of CFCs as the core of sandwich panels was pointed out by Ashrafian et al. [65]. They fabricated a couple of unbalanced/balanced sandwich structures with cores of pure PLA accordion cellular structure and glass fiber-reinforced ones. Their experimental findings showed an enhancement of about 150 % due to

employment of the CFCs accordion core in balanced configuration. Li et al. [66] assessed flexural response of integrated 3D printed sandwich panels with fiber-reinforced Triply Periodic Minimal Surface core. It was concluded that the proposed integrated 3D printing enhanced the flexural modulus and strength of the sandwich panel. Besides, the integrated 3D printing method prevented the sandwich panel from catastrophic failure during compression test. This matter resulted in more than 160 % absorbed energy in comparison with those fabricated by multi-step 3D printing. Not limited to traditional configurations of cellular structures, Zhai et al. [67] proposed sandwich structures with double-row and crossed pyramidal lattice cores. Performing three-point bending tests, it was computed that the peak load, specific peak load and energy absorption increased by about 10 %, 8 % and 19 %, respectively. Application of cellular structures in sandwich panels was also highlighted by Wang et al. [68] when they studied the bending performance of sandwich panels with sinusoidal corrugated cores. The effects of numerous geometrical parameters including skin thickness, wavelength and core thickness and height on bending response were evaluated by means of experiments and Finite-Element Analysis (FEA) simulations. For the next step, designing the core of this sandwich panel with fiber-reinforced sinusoidal corrugated core should be launched. In summary, a brief but quantitative comparison between the mechanical properties of traditional cellular structures and CFCs is presented in Table 1.

Building on these performance enhancements, Section 2.2 presents a systematic taxonomy of CFCs architectures, spanning honeycomb, chiral, and rotating-cell motifs. It further examines how geometric design and Poisson-ratio engineering govern macroscopic mechanical and multifunctional behaviors.

2.2. Topological & functional classification

CFCs can be classified both by their spatial configuration, into 2D and 3D architectures; and by their effective Poisson's ratio, which governs deformation kinematics and underpins many functional properties, as illustrated in Fig. 5. Planar CFCs include classic honeycomb lattices, chiral geometries, and rotating-plate motifs, each defined by distinct cell topologies and ligament connectivity [74,75]. Fully three-dimensional lattices such as pyramidal trusses, spring networks,

Table 1

A quantitative comparison between the reported mechanical properties of some traditional cellular structures and CFCs.

Lattice structure	Reported mechanical properties	
	Pure material	Continuous fiber-reinforced material
Negative Poisson's ratio Polyamide (PA) lattice reinforced by continuous carbon fibers [69]	Compressive peak stress 1.9–2.2 MPa	Compressive peak stress 7.8–8.3 MPa
Continuous fiber reinforced Polyactic Acid (PLA) [47]	Elastic modulus 131 GPa	Elastic modulus 565 GPa
	Compression modulus 16.08 MPa	Compression modulus 3.195 MPa
	Poisson's ratio -0.82	Poisson's ratio -0.89
	Energy absorption (J/m³) 0.43	Energy absorption (J/m³) 0.23
	Damage behavior Struts were failed prematurely and whole structure was collapsed, suddenly	Damage behavior Continuous fibers prohibited propagation of cracks in the matrix and breakage of struts
Recoverable honeycomb composites reinforced by continuous carbon fibers [70]	Specific stiffness (kN.m/kg) Longitudinal: 125 Transverse: 165	Specific stiffness (kN.m/kg) Longitudinal: 190 Transverse: 425
	Specific energy absorption (J/g) Longitudinal: 1.88 Transverse: 1.58	Specific energy absorption (J/g) Longitudinal: 5.32 Transverse: 3.35
fiber reinforced diamond cellular structural composites [38]	Diamond-infill CFRCSCs (Pure PLA) Young's module (MPa) 444.95	Diamond-infill CFRCSCs (Kevlar fiber) Young's module (MPa) 900.62
	Tensile strength (MPa) 7.33	Tensile strength (MPa) 19.48
	Average specific strength (KN·m/kg) 15.41	Average specific strength (KN·m/kg) 32.51
Glass fiber-reinforced cruciform honeycomb [71]	Pure PLA honeycomb Tensile stiffnesses (MPa) X-direction: 34.9 Y-direction: 222.1 In-plane Poisson's ratio 0.0623	Glass fiber-Reinforced PLA Honeycomb Tensile stiffnesses (MPa) X-direction: 70.1 Y-direction: 361.9 In-plane Poisson's ratio 0.0717
Glass fiber/PA12 composite lattice structures [72]	Tensile strength (MPa) 34.77	Tensile strength (MPa) 40.75
	Elastic modulus (MPa) 1992.08	Elastic modulus (MPa) 3626.45
		Deformation behavior The reinforced samples can undergo repeated loading without obvious deformation
Glass fiber-reinforced nylon honeycomb structures [39]	Flexural strength (MPa) 45	Flexural strength (MPa) Nylon/GF central: 75 Nylon/GF 2-4: 110
	Flexural stiffness (MPa) 950	Flexural stiffness (MPa) Nylon/GF central: 2500 Nylon/GF 2-4: 5000
		Failure concerns Using the 3D printing method, the porosity between matrix and fibers was decreased and better structural integrity was achieved
PA and carbon fiber-reinforced polymer cellular structures (gyroid, honeycomb, Voronoi) [40]	Elastic modulus (MPa) Honeycomb: 25.9 Gyroid: 18.4 Voronoi: 49.3	Elastic modulus (MPa) Honeycomb: 241 Gyroid: 113 Voronoi: 461
	Compressive yield stress (MPa) Honeycomb: 1.65	Compressive yield stress (MPa) Honeycomb: 6.66

Table 1 (continued)

Lattice structure	Reported mechanical properties	
	Pure material	Continuous fiber-reinforced material
Triply periodic minimum surface (TPMS)-based lattice structures (Diamond, Gyroid, Primitive) [73]	Gyroid: 1.14 Voronoi: 2.18	Gyroid: 3.48 Voronoi: 11.2
	Compressive modulus (GPa) (Relative density: 23 %)	Compressive modulus (GPa) (Relative density: 23 %)
	Diamond: 0.261 Gyroid: 0.0207 Primitive: 0.085	Diamond: 0.292 Gyroid: 0.228 Primitive: 0.111
	Peak strength (MPa) (Relative density: 23 %)	Peak strength (MPa) (Relative density: 23 %)
	Diamond: 8.71 Gyroid: 5.78 Primitive: 2.95	Diamond: 8.83 Gyroid: 5.63 Primitive: 3.02

and grid frameworks leverage spatially complex geometries to achieve unprecedented weight savings and tailored mechanical performance [76,77]. These 3D architectures, enabled by advanced additive and in-situ consolidation methods, permit the design of load-bearing components with intricate internal features that resist fatigue [78], optimize aerodynamics or hydrodynamics, and withstand harsh environmental conditions in marine, aerospace, and transportation applications.

Besides being classified based on their two-dimensional or three-dimensional configurations, CFCs can also be categorized according to their Poisson's ratio. Conventional honeycomb CFCs exhibit a positive Poisson's ratio, contracting laterally under axial tension. Accordion-style lattices approach zero Poisson's ratio, offering nearly constant cross-section under load. This is a characteristic exploited in morphing-wing concepts where disparate in-plane stiffnesses are required [79–81]. Auxetic CFCs, with negative Poisson's ratios, expand laterally when stretched and contract under compression, yielding higher indentation resistance, enhanced shear moduli, improved fracture toughness, and synclastic curvature under bending [79–81]. This unique behavior enables dome-shaped sandwich skins [82], vibro-acoustic damping elements [82,83], and tubular devices such as stents and annuloplasty rings; especially the ones that are designed to maintain luminal patency, reduce migration, and resist kinking under bending loads in cardiovascular applications [29,84–87]. Auxetic scaffolds further mimic the mechanical environment of biological tissues in bone-tissue engineering [88], while in textiles and sports equipment, they conform dynamically to body contours and enable size-reduction strategies [89–91]. Their tunable pore structure also benefits adaptive filtration systems [92]. Subsection 2.2.1 examines planar CFCs topologies, their Poisson-ratio categories, and the trade-offs between mechanical performance and manufacturability. Subsection 2.2.2 then surveys recent advances in true 3D CFCs. This includes novel printing paradigms that overcome the limitations of layer-by-layer approaches.

2.2.1. 2D CFCs

Table 2 catalogs representative 2D CFCs from recent literature, organized by base topology (honeycomb, chiral, rotating-plate), Poisson's-ratio class (positive, zero, negative), and primary mechanical and fabrication attributes. Conventional honeycombs, with positive Poisson's ratios, deliver reliable flexural and in-plane stiffness but lack auxetic benefits. Near-zero-Poisson cells, typically accordion-style, enable constant cross-sectional profiles under load, desirable in morphing and deployable structures. 2D Auxetic lattices dominate recent studies due to their productibility by FEM and superior energy-absorption capacity. Opening narrower ligaments under compression and closing under tension concentrates deformation in cell corners, thereby increasing plastic dissipation. While auxetic cells can incur higher manufacturing complexity, their exceptional indentation resistance and tailored failure modes make them attractive for impact-mitigation and adaptive structures.

Fig. 5. Classification of CFCs based of geometry and mechanical response.

2.2.2. 3D CFCs

The fabrication of 3D CFCs with continuous fibers poses unique challenges: uninterrupted fiber trajectories, support-free printing of overhangs, and managing residual stresses in complex geometries [110, 111]. In-situ consolidation techniques combining fiber deposition and matrix curing have enabled the creation of spring and truss lattices from ultraviolet -curable thermosets [112], as well as ultralight pyramidal-truss sandwich cores via continuous-lattice fabrication [113]. Free-hanging FDM approaches have extended these capabilities to thermoplastic matrices, producing springs, grids, and spatially intricate CFCs without sacrificial supports [33,114]. To eliminate the assembly of partial trusses, spatial 3D printing methods trace continuous fiber paths through open volumes, fabricating multilayer pyramid and grid structures in a single path [115,116]. This paradigm, as shown in Fig. 6, leverages tailored nozzle trajectories and dynamic path planning to maintain fiber continuity through complex overhangs, yielding lightweight architectures with exceptional specific stiffness and strength. Table 3 summarizes these recent advances in 3D CFCs, highlighting the interplay between geometric innovation, fiber routing strategies, and resulting mechanical performance.

By classifying CFCs along these spatial and functional dimensions, and examining both 2D and 3D implementations, we establish a structured foundation for the design of drivers that will be synthesized in Section 3's taxonomy of cell architectures.

3. Core design considerations

In this section, we outline the core design considerations for CFCs. It is to be noted that we separate *structural design* from *optimization* to keep representation distinct from search. Structural design defines the admissible space: unit-cell families, parameterizations, kinematic constraints, fiber-path continuity, manufacturability bounds, and target metrics [118]. Optimization then chooses values in that space through a mathematical program and a solver. This separation is useful in CFCs because many performance limits are set by how the structure is encoded, not by the optimizer. It also permits a mix and match strategy. For example, path-continuous parameterization can pair with gradient, evolutionary, or surrogate methods without rewriting the design model. Many studies blend these steps implicitly. We surface them explicitly, so comparisons are fair and reusable. In Section 3.1, we present the key CFC design approaches, covering structural configurations, material choices, and eco-friendly strategies. Afterwards, in Section 3.2, the FEA simulation of CFCs is reviewed as a tool for extraction of their mechanical properties, energy absorption characteristics and damage

mechanisms. Then, in Section 3.3, we introduce optimization techniques for CFCs, detailing computational methods and parameter tuning to maximize performance.

3.1. Key CFCs design approaches

Building on the taxonomy and design drivers from Section 2, this section describes three principal avenues (see Fig. 7): macroscopic mechanical modelling, eco-friendly shape-memory design, and innovative fabrication schemes.

3.1.1. Investigations on macroscopic mechanical behavior of CFCs

As demonstrated in Fig. 8, some investigations focused on the macroscopic mechanical behavior of CFCs in the frameworks of analytical analysis, experimental approach, and finite element simulations. An extended theoretical model based on the classical laminate theory was presented to predict the equivalent properties and onset of failure for a fiber-reinforced re-entrant unit cell in [96]. In contrast to prior research, this study treated each strut of the unit cell as a composite laminate, predicting the elastic stress related to buckling instability and identifying the failure point. The impact of geometric parameters on the elastic constants of the re-entrant lattice was also examined. The strength of the unit cell, considering both buckling and damage, was ultimately evaluated using the proposed relations and compared to the finite element results. Further, an analytical model based on classical laminate theory was also proposed to predict the equivalent elastic properties of honeycomb composite structures in [97]. This study showed that fiber-reinforced Poly Lactic Acid (PLA) outperformed pure isotropic materials in terms of rigidity and strength. They also explored the use of commingled yarn in place of single yarn for fiberglass struts, finding an increase in ultimate tensile strength.

Compression tests on polyurethane foam-filled and hollow honeycomb structures highlighted their energy absorption capacity. The failure pattern analysis revealed fractures at a 45° angle, with experimental results showing a 128 % increase in tensile strength and a 21 % improvement in failure strain for structures reinforced with commingled fiberglass. The mechanical performance and failure response of honeycombs reinforced with carbon fibers under compressive loading was investigated in [70]. To fabricate the bone-inspired composite honeycombs from a continuous carbon fiber bundle, a customized 3D printer, adapted from a commercial Fused-Filament Fabrication (FFF) platform, was employed. The results showed a notable increase in compressive strength and energy absorption, with the maximum values observed at 20 % fiber content. In addition, it was observed that the failure modes

Table 2
List of 2D CFCs in the recent literature.

Types of 2D CFCs	Advantages	Limitations	Mechanical performance evaluation
Hybrid composite sandwich [93] 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ■ Lightweight ■ High flexural modulus ■ High flexural strength 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ■ Heavy reliance on the quality of additive manufacturing ■ Wall thickness constraints 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ■ Three-point bending test and Bending loads ■ FEA
Interlocked triangular honeycomb [94] 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ■ High strength ■ High stiffness 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ■ High bonding requirements ■ High structural reinforcement requirements ■ Edge effect 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ■ Three-point bending and edge compression tests
Composite periodic cellular structure [95] 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ■ Pattern transformation capability 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ■ Largely depends on specific material combinations and their properties 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ■ Uniaxial compression test and FEA
CFRTPC auxetic honeycomb [47] 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ■ High energy absorption ■ High compressive stiffness ■ Small Poisson ratio 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ■ Printing may cause fiber misalignment, pullout, and fiber-free matrix areas 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ■ Uniaxial compression loading tests ■ In-plane compression FEA
Re-entrant composite honeycomb structures [96] 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ■ High energy absorption ■ High impact resistance ■ Enhanced indentation resistance ■ Enhanced shear modulus 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ■ Dependence on cell angle for optimal performance ■ Buckling and damage susceptibility 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ■ Axial/shear loading analyzed in analytical models and FEA
Composite honeycomb Structures [97] 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ■ High elastic properties High strength ■ High energy absorption 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ■ Reduced stiffness after the initial failure mode ■ Deformation capacity limits use in high-strain applications 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ■ Compression and tensile test and FEA
Recoverable honeycomb composite [70] 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ■ High energy absorption ■ High stiffness ■ Shape recovery capability 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ■ Potential complexity in manufacturing ■ Recovery effect is not entirely reversible 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ■ Longitudinal and transverse compression tests
Bone-inspired composite cellular structure [98] 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ■ High stiffness-to-weight ratio ■ High energy absorption 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ■ Potential complexity in manufacturing 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ■ Axial compression and shear tests

(continued on next page)

Table 2 (continued)

Types of 2D CFCSS	Advantages	Limitations	Mechanical performance evaluation
<p>Orthotropic accordion cellular honeycomb [99]</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ■ High transverse stiffness ■ High flexibility for morphing applications ■ High energy absorption ■ Zero in-plane Poisson's ratio ■ High effective elastic modulus 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ■ Potential complexity in manufacturing 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ■ Tensile Tests
<p>Continuous Carbon Fiber (CCF) composite structures [69]</p>		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ■ Potential complexity in manufacturing ■ Trade-off between stiffness and auxetic behavior 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ■ Quasi-static compression test
<p>Cruciform honeycomb [71]</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ■ High elastic modulus ■ Tailored Poisson's ratios, load distribution and energy absorption 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ■ High sensitivity to the angles of the cells 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ■ Tensile test
<p>Diamond cellular structure [38]</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ■ High tensile properties ■ Lightweight 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ■ Print path/layer thickness can significantly affect mechanical properties 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ■ Tensile test
<p>Cellular structural composite [100]</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ■ High bending strength ■ High flexural modulus 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ■ Requires precise control over structural parameters 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ■ Uniaxial tensile test, ■ Axial displacement loads FEA
<p>Fiber-reinforced composite honeycomb [60]</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ■ Shape memory ■ High energy absorption 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ■ Requires activation temperature control 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ■ Out-of-Plane and In-Plane compression tests, ■ Tensile and shear loading FEA
<p>4D printed cellular structure [53]</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ■ Shape memory effect ■ High tensile strength 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ■ Trade-off between fiber content and shape memory performance 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ■ Uniaxial tensile and thermal loading test
<p>Composite sandwich structure [49]</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ■ Core density rise ■ Boosted load and flex modulus across all shapes ■ Rhombus core was the strongest 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ■ Requires precise fiber tension control 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ■ Three-point bending ■ Tensile test

(continued on next page)

Table 2 (continued)

Types of 2D CFCSS	Advantages	Limitations	Mechanical performance evaluation
<p>Continuous fiber-reinforced auxetic structure [61]</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ■ Reusability ■ High energy absorption ■ 90 % shape recovery ratio 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ■ Degradation over multiple cycles, ■ Possible stress concentration in rhombus specimens 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ■ Uniaxial compression ■ Cyclic compression-shape memory tests
<p>Composite horseshoe lattice [101]</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ■ Temperature-dependent stiffness and the initial peak load ■ Shape memory effects 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ■ Potential complexity in manufacturing 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ■ Isothermal compression and thermo-mechanical cycle tests
<p>Continuous fiber reinforced thermoplastic negative Poisson's ratio structures [102]</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ■ More fiber crossovers reduced Negative Poisson's ratio ■ Increased stiffness and energy absorption 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ■ Complex printing path 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ■ Uniaxial quasi-static compression tests
<p>Circular honeycomb [103]</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ■ High stiffness-to-weight ratio ■ Energy absorption 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ■ Potential complexity in manufacturing 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ■ Out-of-plane and in-plane compression tests
<p>Composite lattice structure [62]</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ■ Enhanced joint tensile strength ■ Enhanced Young's modulus 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ■ Potential geometric inaccuracies and defects at the joints 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ■ Quasi-static tensile test
<p>Dual-nozzle printed cellular structure [104]</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ■ Efficient material distribution ■ Manufacturing speed ■ High stiffness-to-weight ratios ■ High energy absorption 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ■ Potential defects in manufacturing 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ■ Tensile test ■ Compressive test
<p>Corrugated sandwich structure [105]</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ■ Enhanced shape memory ■ Bending resistance ■ High stiffness-to-weight ratios ■ Mechanical stability 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ■ Geometric parameters significantly impact failure modes and performance 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ■ Quasi-static three-point bending test ■ Compression test
<p>Cellular composite structures (CCS) [106]</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ■ High tensile strength ■ High flexural strength 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ■ Dependency on infill pattern and density for mechanical performance 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ■ Tensile and Flexural tests
<p>Honeycomb structure [107]</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ■ Efficient load distribution ■ High specific load ■ High bending performance 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ■ Sensitivity to fiber distribution and path planning 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ■ Three-point bending test

(continued on next page)

Table 2 (continued)

Types of 2D CFCSS	Advantages	Limitations	Mechanical performance evaluation
 CCF hexagonal frame [108]	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ■ Higher tensile strength ■ Better failure resistance 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ■ Dependency on the aspect ratio and geometric configuration 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ■ Remote tensile loading test
 Double kite-shape cellular structure [109]	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • High stiffness • High strength • Good energy absorption 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ■ Print limitation affects the performance of structure under the tensile loadings 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • In-plane compression tests

Fig. 6. Manufacturing different 3D composite structures by novel winding printing methods [115].

differ significantly under longitudinal and transverse loading due to the directional properties of carbon fibers. Under longitudinal loading, the honeycombs exhibit global deformation and maintain structural integrity while under transverse loading; they show local shear failure. Further, an analytical model utilizing the energy method was extended to calculate the equivalent stiffness of a novel bone-inspired cellular structure made from PLA reinforced by continuous glass fibers [98]. Experimental results, along with finite element simulations, demonstrated that employing continuous glass fibers significantly improved the elastic stiffness of the cellular structure in different directions and affected the damage scenarios in comparison with the structure fabricated with pure material (Fig. 8 (b)). Enhanced equivalent stiffness of 3D printed honeycomb structures with an accordion shape of U-type beams were energetically computed in [99] that were reinforced with glass fibers (Fig. 8 (c)). This kind of structure can be considered in morphing wing applications, where low and high elastic stiffnesses are required along the chord and the span of wings, respectively. Here, a zero Poisson's ratio value was extracted by implementing some straight beams which concluding higher axial stiffness along the perpendicular direction. Moreover, the proposed orthotropic structure had a remarkably greater failure strain when it was loaded in the morphing direction compared to an isotropic configuration. The energy methods were again addressed to calculate the equivalent elastic properties of a glass

fiber-reinforced cruciform cellular structure with high strain response (Fig. 8 (d)) [71]. The 3D-printed composite cellular structure was subjected to experimental analysis and around 60 % enhancement in the axial stiffnesses was reported in comparison with non-reinforced samples. More remarkably, the failure strains of reinforced samples were enhanced seven times rather than those without embedded glass fibers. The authors also mentioned that employing lattice structures with a zero Poisson's ratio unit cell may enhance the flexural properties of the cruciform cellular structure.

FFF technology was employed to produce CFR honeycomb lattices exhibiting pronounced shape-memory characteristics [60]. Under in-plane compression, these lattices developed localized deformation bands that altered stress distribution, and their in-plane energy-absorption efficiency surpassed that of several other cellular configurations [119–130]. A CCF-equipped 3D printer was then used to fabricate sandwich panels with honeycomb, rhombus, rectangular, and circular core geometries [49]. It was demonstrated that equivalent stiffness in CFRTP sandwich structures can be tailored by core shape selection: the rectangular core yielded the highest load-to-density ratio, while the circular core achieved the greatest flexural-modulus-to-density ratio [49]. Cellular composites reinforced with continuous carbon fibers were fabricated via FFF and mechanically characterized using grid and triangular infill patterns at varying

Table 3
List of 3D CFCs in the recent literature.

Types of 3D CFCs	Advantages	Limitations	Mechanical performance evaluation
CCF reinforced thermosetting composites [117]	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ■ High tensile strength, ■ High elastic modulus 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ■ High manufacturing cost 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ■ Tensile and three-point bending conditions
 Continuous fiber-reinforced thermoset composites [112]	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ■ High stiffness ■ High strength 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ■ Complexity of controlling the printing parameters 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ■ Uniaxial tension test, ■ Shear stress analysis
 CCF-PLA pyramidal lattice truss core sandwich structure [33]	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ■ High structural strength 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ■ High PLA viscosity impedes complete fiber bundle impregnation 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ■ Out-of-plane compression tests ■ Morphological analysis post-testing
 Lattice truss sandwich structure [114]	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ■ High compressive strength ■ High compressive modulus ■ Self-monitoring capabilities 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ■ Lower cyclic load performance ■ Printing path inaccuracy 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ■ Monotonic out-of-plane compression and cyclic loading tests
 Ultra-lightweight load-bearing structures [113]	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ■ High stiffness-density ratio ■ High strength- density ratio ■ Lightweight ■ Self-monitoring capabilities 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ■ Euler buckling in truss struts reduce load capacity ■ Draping issues compromise structural integrity 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ■ Monotonic out-of-plane compression and cyclic loading tests
 Vertically stacked three-layer truss structure [115]	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ■ High structural stability ■ Uniformity in force distribution ■ Low relative density 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ■ Layer parameter differences cause varied load capacities and failure modes 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ■ Compression testing
 45° connected stacked three-layer truss structure [115]	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ■ High structural stability ■ High energy absorption ■ Multi-layer consistent load distribution 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ■ Increased relative density ■ Complexity in design and manufacturing 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ■ Compression testing

densities [106]. Increasing the infill density was shown to significantly enhance mechanical performance, making these composites well suited for applications demanding high strength and stiffness [106]. Finally, hexagonal frames printed with continuous fibers were examined experimentally and numerically to identify failure modes via Hashin's damage parameters [108]. Two primary material failure mechanisms with a consistent failure locus were identified, and it was determined that, beyond micro-constituent properties and micro-defects, geometric configuration exerts a dominant influence on the failure behavior of compliant hexagonal frames [108]. Table 4 states a brief quantitative description of the selected measured mechanical properties of CFCs and compares them with those of unreinforced ones.

3.1.2. Design of environmentally friendly CFCs

Intelligent CFCs with reusable energy-absorption capabilities were developed using 4D printing combined with a cold-programming-induced shape-memory effect [61]. Three cellular designs, i. e., a rhombus-based cell and two auxetic configurations were fabricated to maximize energy absorption and reusability (Fig. 9). Experimental characterization of both shape-memory composites and fiber-reinforced shape-memory composites elucidated the underlying recovery mechanism. Cyclic compression tests confirmed that the Auxetic I design achieved a 99.13 % shape-recovery ratio in the first cycle and maintained over 90 % recovery across five cycles [61]. The temperature-dependent mechanical behaviour and shape-recovery

Fig. 7. Emerging research trends in fiber-reinforced cellular structures (CFCs).

Fig. 8. Impact of CFR on the mechanical performance of multiple 2D cellular structures; (a) honeycomb [70], (b) bone-inspired [98], (c) accordion [99], and (d) cruciform [71] samples.

performance of 4D-printed continuous fiber-reinforced horseshoe lattice structures were examined using a novel printing technique [101]. Rectangular horseshoe lattices with varying cell configurations were produced, and thermo-mechanical cyclic tests demonstrated their ability to fix shapes temporarily and subsequently recover the original form. It was observed that the shape-fixity ratio increased with larger imposed

displacements, while the shape-recovery ratio declined at higher deformations [101].

The compressive nonlinear response of a star hourglass-shaped honeycomb as fabricated from pure PLA and from PLA reinforced with chopped and continuous fibers was evaluated under quasi-static compression followed by thermally activated shape recovery [131].

Table 4
Brief quantitative comparison of multiple CFCs in terms of selected measured elastic properties.

Cellular configuration	The measured mechanical properties				
	E_1 (MPa)	E_2 (MPa)	E_3 (MPa)	G_{12} (MPa)	ν_{12}
Kevlar-Fiber-Reinforced (KFR) PLA re-entrant honeycomb [96]	850 (max)	115 (max)	-	11.8 (max)	-3.2 (min)
	10 (min)	20 (min)		5 (min)	+2 (max)
Glass-Fiber-Reinforced (GFR) PLA accordion honeycomb [99]	50 (max)	4500 (max)	3700 (max)	15 (max)	$2.5e^{-4}$ (max)
	0.015 (min)	1300 (min)	1000 (min)	0.03 (min)	$8e^{-8}$ (min)
Cruciform honeycomb [71]	70 (GFR PLA)	362 (GFR PLA)	-	-	$7.17e^{-2}$ (GFR PLA)
	35 (Pure PLA)	222 (pure PLA)			$6.23e^{-2}$ (Pure PLA)
	17.4 (max)	-	-	-	-
CFR PLA Grid infill structure [106]	16.2 (min)				
CFR PLA triangular infill structure [106]	16.2 (max)				
	14.8 (min)				
KFR diamond shape cellular structure [53]	445 (Pure PLA)				
	900 (KRF PLA)				
CFR triangle-filled structure [102]	3300 (max)				
	1125 (min)				
Negative Poisson's ratio structure with rotating squares [47]	19 (max)				
	16 (min)				
CFR PLA auxetic honeycomb [47]	31.95 (CFR PLA)	24.85 (CFR PLA)			-0.89 (CFR PLA)
	16.08 (Pure PLA)	13.34 (Pure PLA)			-0.82 (Pure PLA)
	1175 (CFR PA)				
CFR PA high elastic stiffness lattice [69]	120 (Pure PA)				
	27 (CFR PA)				-0.1 (CFR PA)
CFR PA high negative Poisson's ratio lattice [69]	9 (Pure PA)				-0.26 (Pure PA)

Specimens were produced via FDM using both unreinforced and fiber-reinforced PLA filaments. A combined experimental and finite-element modeling approach demonstrated that the inherent nonlinear behavior of PLA under tension and compression significantly affects post-recovery energy-absorption. The results indicate that by optimizing auxetic geometry, cell dimensions, and fiber-reinforcement strategy, one can design lattices that recover their original shape after deformation and maintain high energy-absorption performance through successive load-recovery cycles [131]. Given this insight into the impact of fiber reinforcement on the energy absorption capacity, multiple cellular structures are listed in Table 5 and are compared in terms of their experimentally obtained specific energy absorptions.

3.1.3. Innovative fabrication schemes for CFCs

The challenges associated with fabricating 2D CFCs using continuous fibers, particularly for chiral and rotating-plate architectures, have led researchers to concentrate on honeycomb variants, where typical configurations and mechanical performance can be more readily assessed without addressing the broader gamut of auxetic behaviors [132]. Traditional fabrication routes for fiber-reinforced cellular composites often involve high-cost equipment and precision molds, limiting scalability and design complexity. In contrast, an innovative interlocking approach was employed to create a composite interlocked triangular honeycomb and its corresponding sandwich panel [94]. This methodology yielded structures whose equivalent stiffness and strength exceeded those of interlocked Kagome and square honeycombs fabricated from the same base material. Moreover, the sandwich configuration achieved over a 20 % increase in specific strength and nearly a threefold enhancement in specific stiffness compared to aluminum honeycomb sandwiches [94]. Nonetheless, the intrinsic constraints of conventional fabrication techniques continue to impede wider adoption and the realization of more intricate CFCs geometries.

Designing appropriate printing paths is critical for two-dimensional CFCs because continuous fibers cannot “jump” between layers; fiber orientation and connectivity are dictated entirely by the chosen tool-path. If fibers are not routed through core-lap regions, weak zones with minimal or absent fiber reinforcement can emerge, compromising mechanical integrity. A novel composite cellular architecture incorporating thin interfacial layers was introduced to lower the critical strain required for pattern transformation under compression; thereby achieving a value below that of comparable single-material periodic lattices [95]. In parallel, auxetic honeycombs fabricated from Continuous Fiber-Reinforced Thermoplastic Composite (CFRTPC) and pure PLA were examined through experimental testing and finite-element analysis [133]. Compared to unreinforced PLA specimens, CFRTPC auxetic lattices exhibited higher compressive stiffness and increased specific energy absorption along both principal directions, despite only a marginal mass increase. Moreover, continuous fibers inhibited crack propagation within the matrix, thereby enhancing structural integrity and preventing premature failure under load [133]. A comprehensive structural-topology-driven approach was developed to fabricate continuous-fiber composites via FFF, wherein topological configurations were tailored to specific performance objectives and continuous fibers were aligned along average load paths during printing [69]. This methodology yielded significant gains in effective stiffness, compressive strength, and negative Poisson's ratio for polyamide specimens containing CCF and identified an optimal fiber volume fraction that maximized both negative Poisson's behavior and elastic modulus [69].

There are some available innovative techniques in the literature to resolve manufacturing-related defects of 3D printed CFCs as shown in Fig. 10. A novel technique for producing continuous-fiber-reinforced diamond lattices via FFF demonstrated predictable, reliable tensile properties, with systematic analysis of printing paths and structural parameters used to optimize tensile performance [38]. Kevlar-reinforced cellular composites were fabricated by feeding Kevlar and PLA filaments simultaneously into an FDM printer. Three-point bending tests revealed that Kevlar fibers improved mechanical properties, and that rhombus-shaped unit cells, by providing varied fiber orientations, exhibited superior bending resistance compared to other cell topologies [100]. In a related study, a triangular Kevlar/PLA cellular lattice with uniformly distributed fibers showed that increasing fiber content to 16.32 % raised breaking strength but reduced shape-memory effectiveness; by adjusting layer thickness and fiber fraction, a balance between tensile strength and shape-memory performance was achieved [53]. Rotating-squares lattices exhibiting negative Poisson's-ratio behavior were printed using a Eulerian-path-based nozzle trajectory to ensure continuous fiber deposition; uniaxial compression tests confirmed a strong negative Poisson's ratio and demonstrated a direct correlation between elastic modulus and hinge stiffness, with greater

Fig. 9. 4D printing as a method toward environmentally friendly CFCSs; (a) reusability of energy absorption capacity [61], (b) shape fixity/recovery under thermomechanical loads [101].

fiber concentration at hinges yielding higher elastic moduli [102]. The effect of stacking direction on 3D-printed CCF-reinforced circular honeycomb integrity was examined via quasi-static compression, revealing that micro voids and weak fiber–matrix interfaces predominantly governed failure modes [103].

Further innovations in manufacturing processes have targeted the inherent weaknesses of multi-step fabrication and single-matrix systems. For instance, an integrated 3D printing method for sandwich panels directly fabricates the core and fiber-reinforced face sheets as a single, monolithic structure. This approach eliminates the brittle adhesive interfaces common in conventional assembly, thereby mitigating catastrophic delamination and significantly enhancing energy absorption through superior core-to-face-sheet fusion [66]. Similarly, a bi-matrix co-extrusion technique addresses poor fiber impregnation by combining thermoset pre-impregnated fibers with a thermoplastic binder during printing [134]. This hybrid material system ensures excellent fiber wetting and reduces porosity, while also enabling the strategic layering of dissimilar fibers such as carbon and basalt to create composites with tailored properties [135]. Another manufacturing technology was introduced by Wu et al. [136] to fabricate Nacre-like carbon fiber-reinforced biomimetic ceramic composites. High-strength and high-toughness carbon fiber-reinforced bionic composites were produced using vat photopolymerization technology. It overcame some challenges of additive manufacturing in producing complex bionic structures. In comparison with solid ceramic material, the resulting structure exhibited more than 293 % and 109 % flexural strength and fracture toughness, respectively.

An adaptive process-planning strategy for continuous-fiber composite lattice joints tested six distinct print-path schemes. The most effective approach, namely, interlocking fibers at strut corners, significantly improved mechanical properties, as validated against horseshoe and auxetic metamaterial configurations [62]. A dual-nozzle FFF method was introduced to double the theoretical print speed for continuous-fiber-reinforced cellular structures; mechanical testing showed only a 6 % difference in properties between single- and dual-nozzle prints, demonstrating that high-speed production can be achieved without compromising structural performance [104]. Incorporating shape-memory polymers into FFF-printed continuous-fiber corrugated sandwich structures enabled thermally activated recovery [137]. Three-point bending tests highlighted the influence of corrugation geometry on mechanical response, and failure-mechanism mapping accurately predicted bending-induced failure modes [105]. Finally, diamond-filled Carbon-Fiber-Reinforced Polymer (CFRP) honeycomb sandwich panels were fabricated using four distinct print-path corner configurations (45°, 90°, and 135°). Here, three-point bending experiments showed that fiber dislocation patterns at different corner angles critically affect bending resistance, providing guidelines for optimizing print-path planning in high-performance CFRP Honeycomb Structures [107]. This foundation highlights the critical role of cell geometry, fiber

continuity, and processing parameters in achieving target mechanical responses. With these structural and functional drivers defined, the subsequent focus shifts to formalizing the search for optimal CFCS architectures. Section 3.3 introduces the principal optimization techniques, ranging from single-scale topology searches to fiber-orientation strategies and fully coupled multiscale formulations. These are used to systematically tailor both lattice layouts and reinforcement patterns for next-generation performance.

3.2. FEA simulations to predict the mechanical behavior of CFCSs

Conducting FEA simulation is essential when the geometry of a structure is somewhat complex and performing so many experiments is not cost-effective [138]. In the case of CFCSs, FEA can be considered as a useful tool to predict their mechanical properties and behaviors including, stiffness, strength, buckling and snap-through, progressive damage and failure and energy absorption. As listed in Table 6, there are two distinct approaches to compute the mechanical response of CFCSs using FEM. The first approach was addressed by Farrokhbadi et al. in [99] and [139] where they employed equivalent elastic properties to extract the macro-scale behaviors of CFCSs with an isotropic plasticity model. For this purpose, the stress-strain behavior of fiber-reinforced polymeric material is extracted using a tensile test on standard coupon tests. This approach is appropriate to predict the macroscopic mechanical response of CFCSs without any consideration of the interface between continuous fibers and matrix material. On the other hand, there are some other studies in the literature that modeled fibers and matrix material in CFCSs, separately [47,53]. Accordingly, two material models are defined for the matrix material and reinforcing fibers. Using this approach, a more precise description of the mechanical properties of CFCSs is obtained and microscopic phenomena at the fiber/matrix interface can be studied. The computational cost is a key issue that dictates which approach is chosen. Apart from these two approaches, a novel multi-scale theoretical model has been developed by Li et al. [140] to analyze intra-laminar properties and damage evolution in stitched composites. By combining continuum damage mechanics and cohesive zone modeling, this theoretical model was enabled to predict mode I fracture behavior and low-velocity impact response. So, this multiscale model may open a new window to study the failure mechanisms of CFCSs and their post-failure behavior.

3.3. Optimization techniques for CFCSs

Building on the design primitives above, we organize optimization in CFCSs by what is being optimized rather than by the solver. The three branches follow the main decision variables and the scale at which they act: cellular structure optimization, fiber orientation optimization, and multiscale concurrent optimization. Cellular structure optimization targets unit cell topology, grading, and geometry. Fiber orientation

Table 5
Brief quantitative comparison of multiple CFCs in terms of energy absorption capability.

Cellular configuration	Base material	Specific energy absorption	
		Pure material	Continuous fiber-reinforced material
Hexagonal honeycomb [70]	PLA	1.88 J/g (longitudinal) 1.58 J/g (transverse)	5.32 J/g (longitudinal) 3.35 J/g (transverse)
Hexagonal and rectangular honeycombs [60]	PLA	-	<u>Hexagonal</u> 10 J/g (max) 4.8 J/g (min) <u>Rectangular</u> 5 J/g (max) 2 J/g (min)
Hexagonal honeycomb [129]	Nylon 12	0.850 J/g (max) 0.141 J/g (min)	-
Auxetic cellular-type I [61]	PLA/ Thermoplastic Polyurethane (TPU) blend	--	0.28 J/g (1st load cycle) 0.16 J/g (1st recovery) 0.1 J/g (2nd recovery) 0.073 J/g (3rd recovery) 0.058 J/g (4th recovery)
Auxetic cellular-type II [61]	PLA/TPU blend	-	0.325 J/g (1st load cycle) 0.174 J/g (1st recovery) 0.122 J/g (2nd recovery) 0.09 J/g (3rd recovery) 0.025 J/g (4th recovery)
Star hourglass honeycomb [131]	PLA	0.75 kPa/g (1st load cycle) 0.66 kPa/g (1st load recovery) 0.56 kPa/g (2nd load recovery)	1.18 kPa/g (1st load cycle) 0.64 kPa/g (1st load recovery) 0.55 kPa/g (2nd load recovery)
Hexagonal honeycomb [51]	Nylon	0.637 J/g (in-plane loading) 0.766 (axial loading)	-
	Onyx	1.889 J/g (in-plane loading) 1.878 (axial loading)	-
Auxetic re-entrant honeycomb [51]	Nylon	0.352 J/g (in-plane loading) 0.463 J/g (axial loading)	-
	Onyx	1.392 J/g (in-plane loading) 1.549 J/g (axial loading)	-
Double arrowhead lattice [51]	Nylon	1.045 J/g (in-plane loading) 1.244 J/g (axial loading)	-
	Onyx	4.254 J/g (in-plane loading) 2.872 J/g (axial loading)	-
CFR PLA auxetic honeycomb [47]	PLA	0.23 MJ/m ³ (1st-direction) 0.28 MJ/m ³ (2nd-direction)	0.43 MJ/m ³ (1st-direction) 0.56 MJ/m ³ (2nd-direction)

optimization treats the fiber path as a spatial trajectory and tunes its direction and continuity. Multiscale concurrent optimization couples these levels and captures interactions between process and performance.

Algorithms such as Solid Isotropic Material with Penalization (SIMP), level set, bidirectional evolutionary structural optimization, gradient methods, evolutionary search, Bayesian optimization, and learning based surrogates are not categories in themselves. They are tools that can operate inside any of the three lenses. Size and shape optimization, process planning, path smoothing, robust or reliability-based formulations, and multi objective tradeoffs are cross cutting and are discussed where relevant. Edge cases such as hierarchical lattices, stacking sequence tuning, or printing strategy optimization are mapped to the closest branch by their primary decision variables. This scheme avoids duplication and keeps the discussion focused.

3.3.1. Cellular structures optimization

The optimization of cellular structures, such as honeycombs, lattice frameworks, and hierarchical designs, is a crucial focus in engineering due to their unique mechanical properties, lightweight nature, and energy absorption capabilities. These structures have been widely adopted in aerospace, automotive, and biomedical fields, where achieving high strength-to-weight ratios, enhanced energy dissipation, and tailored functionalities are essential. Recent advancements in computational methods and additive manufacturing have significantly expanded the possibilities for designing and optimizing cellular structures, enabling the development of intricate geometries and multifunctional components [142]. The early approaches to optimizing cellular structures relied heavily on analytical methods, often grounded in Gibson and Ashby's foundational work on cellular solids [2]. These methods focused on understanding the relationships between relative density, cell topology, and material properties [143]. Hexagonal honeycombs with specific geometric parameters were shown to achieve optimal stiffness and strength for a given material density [2]. More recent optimization strategies leverage advanced computational techniques, such as topology optimization, response surface methods, and meta-modeling frameworks like Kriging and radial basis functions [143]. These methods enable designers to model complex, nonlinear relationships between design variables and performance metrics, such as energy absorption or structural stability [144]. For instance, it was demonstrated that Kriging-based surrogate models coupled with finite element simulations provide robust predictions for optimizing the crashworthiness of hexagonal honeycomb cells [145,146].

The honeycomb structure, a hallmark of cellular designs, has undergone extensive optimization to improve its mechanical properties. Traditional honeycomb structures with uniform wall thickness exhibit excellent in-plane stiffness but can suffer from localized stress concentrations at cell joints under dynamic loading. To address this, researchers have introduced variations such as graded cell walls and thickened joints, which enhance stress distribution and energy absorption [144]. A honeycomb with thickened joints was developed in [147], demonstrating that adjusting parameters such as joint thickness and relative density improved the equivalent elastic modulus by up to 30 % compared to uniform honeycombs [145]. Similarly, hierarchical honeycombs, which combine different cell sizes or geometries within a single structure, have shown improved crash resistance and better utilization of material [148]. Lattice structures, characterized by their interconnected struts and nodes, have become a focal point in cellular structure optimization due to their exceptional specific strength and stiffness. These structures are often optimized using topology optimization algorithms, which iteratively refine the geometry to maximize performance metrics while minimizing material usage [147]. Here, lattice optimization approaches are classified into three categories: geometric unit cell design, mathematical algorithm-based generation, and topology-driven methods [149]. Among these, topology optimization has proven particularly effective for designing lightweight aerospace and biomedical components. For example, graded lattice designs,

Fig. 10. Innovative schemes to resolve manufacturing-related defects in CFCs; (a), (b) Improving the mechanical performance of CFCs through redesign of printing paths [38,53]; (c), (d) methods for enhancing the integrity of joints in CFCs [102,107].

where cell size and density vary spatially, have been shown to outperform uniform lattices in energy absorption applications [149].

The integration of additive manufacturing has revolutionized the optimization of cellular structures by enabling the fabrication of complex, optimized geometries that were previously infeasible with traditional manufacturing methods. This allows for the realization of graded, hierarchical, and topologically optimized structures with high precision and minimal material waste [150]. Researchers have used such approaches to fabricate lattice structures with tailored stiffness and energy absorption properties. The role of additive manufacturing in creating multi-functional cellular designs was highlighted in [151], such as honeycombs for aerospace and re-entrant auxetic lattices for crash-worthiness applications [108]. Moreover, such techniques have facilitated the development of multi-scale designs, where macroscale topology optimization is complemented by microscale cell optimization [150]. A list of optimization methods for cellular structures is presented in Table 7.

3.3.2. Fiber-orientation optimization

Fiber-orientation optimization is a pivotal area in the design and development of composite materials, especially for applications demanding high strength, stiffness, and tailored mechanical properties. The anisotropic nature of fiber-reinforced composites, where properties such as tensile strength and stiffness vary with fiber alignment, makes the optimization of fiber orientation essential for enhancing structural performance under specific loading conditions. Advances in computational techniques and manufacturing methods, such as 3D printing and robotic fiber placement, have significantly expanded the possibilities for optimizing fiber orientations. Traditional laminates typically feature fibers aligned along fixed, linear orientations, resulting in constant stiffness properties. However, variable stiffness laminates introduce spatially varying fiber orientations, allowing designers to tailor stiffness at a microscale level to specific loading paths. Workflows for the design and manufacture of such structures were developed in [153], leveraging topology optimization and advanced robotic placement methods. Their

work demonstrated that by varying fiber orientation within each layer, structures could achieve up to 30 % higher stiffness compared to constant stiffness laminates [153]. In the realm of curvilinear fiber paths, approaches like streamline-based optimization have gained traction. Here, fibers are aligned along the principal stress trajectories, maximizing the load-bearing capacity. Studies have shown that composites with curvilinear fibers significantly outperform those with traditional linear fiber orientations under complex loading scenarios [154].

Optimization of fiber orientations often involves coupling finite element analysis with advanced optimization algorithms [140]. Continuous Fiber Angle Optimization is a widely used method where finite elements are assigned both material density and fiber orientation as optimization variables. This method iteratively aligns fibers with principal stress directions, though it is prone to local optima issues [153]. Discrete Material Optimization, another prevalent approach, offers higher computational stability by assigning discrete orientation angles to each element. This reduces design freedom but avoids the convergence issues of the continuous fiber approach. Discrete Material Optimization has been effectively applied to optimize laminates for stiffness and stress distribution under dynamic loading [154]. Genetic algorithms and particle swarm optimization (have also been employed for multi-objective optimization of fiber orientation. The use of Genetic Algorithms to optimize fiber length and content in coir-vinyl ester composites, achieved significant improvements in tensile and flexural strength [155]. These heuristic methods are particularly effective for non-linear, high-dimensional problems where gradient-based approaches may struggle [156]. Additive manufacturing has revolutionized the optimization of fiber orientations, facilitating the fabrication of complicated geometries and tailored fiber paths. Studies have shown that 3D-printed continuous fiber-reinforced composites can achieve up to 305 % higher strength compared to conventionally printed composites by optimizing fiber orientations to align with principal stress trajectories [155]. For example, 3D printing of diamond cellular composites with optimized fiber paths demonstrated superior tensile properties due to uniform fiber distribution and strategy [19]. Multiple

Table 6
Different categories of FEA simulations of CFCs with details.

Description of cellular structure	Reported features of FEA simulations
<i>FEA with equivalent material properties</i>	
Mechanical characterization of a continuous glass fiber-reinforced nylon cellular structure [39]	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ■ Software: ANSYS ■ Material model: Multilinear isotropic hardening plasticity
Elastic properties of a continuous glass fiber-reinforced accordion cellular structure [99]	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ■ Software: ABAQUS (version 2020) ■ Element type: 20-node quadratic brick element (C3D20) ■ Material model: Equivalent laminate elastic properties ■ Boundary conditions: Symmetric and antisymmetric boundary conditions to the edges of the unit cell
Energy absorption of a continuous glass-fiber-reinforced accordion cellular structure [139]	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ■ Software: ABAQUS (version 2020) ■ Loading type: Displacement-based compression on one side ■ Loading rate: 1 mm/s ■ Gripping conditions: Two rigid plates ■ Element type: 20-node quadratic brick element (C3D20) ■ Material model: Equivalent laminate elastic properties + isotropic hardening plasticity for PLA ■ Boundary conditions: All DOFs were restricted on one side
Characterization of a 3D carbon fiber-reinforced re-entrant auxetic cellular structure [141]	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ■ Software: ABAQUS/Explicit ■ Loading type: Displacement-based compression on one side ■ Loading rate: 0.5 mm/min ■ Gripping conditions: Two discrete rigid plates with reference points ■ Element type: 8-node linear incompatible elements (C3D8I) ■ Material model: Equivalent elastic properties of unidirectional carbon/epoxy (T700/ epoxy) laminate ■ Interactions: Surface-to-surface contacts are defined between the plates and the specimen ■ Boundary conditions: All DOFs were restricted on one side
Elastic properties of a glass fiber-reinforced cruciform honeycomb structure [71]	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ■ Software: ABAQUS (version 2020) ■ Loading type: Displacement-based tension on one side ■ Gripping conditions: A rigid plate one side ■ Material model: Equivalent elastic properties + isotropic hardening plasticity ■ Element type: twenty-node quadratic brick elements ■ Boundary conditions: 5 mm tensile displacement on one side. All DOFs were restricted on the other side
<i>FEA with fiber and matrix material properties</i>	
In-plane behaviors of a continuous fiber-reinforced composite auxetic honeycomb structure [47]	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ■ Software: ABAQUS (version 6.14-1) ■ Loading type: Displacement-based compression on one side ■ Loading rate: 0.5 mm/ms ■ Gripping conditions: Two rigid plates ■ Material model for fibers: Linear elastic + perfect plastic ■ Material model for matrix: Linear elastic + isotropic hardening plasticity ■ Element type for matrix and fiber: Eight-node hexahedral linear reduced integration elements (C3D8R) ■ Interactions: General contact, ALL WITH SELF

Table 6 (continued)

Description of cellular structure	Reported features of FEA simulations
Mechanical properties of a 4D printed continuous fiber-reinforced cellular structure [53]	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ■ Contact method: Penalty with 0.2 friction coefficient ■ Contact between matrix and fiber bundles: Co-node connection ■ Boundary conditions: All DOFs were restricted on the other side ■ Software: ABAQUS (version 2018) ■ Loading type: Displacement-based tension on one side ■ Boundary conditions: All DOFs were restricted on one side

methods of fiber-orientation optimization for cellular structures are presented in Table 8.

3.3.3. Multiscale concurrent optimization

Building on the principles of cellular structure and fiber orientation optimization, multiscale concurrent optimization represents a transformative methodology for designing materials and structures that maximize performance across scales. Unlike traditional approaches that decouple macroscopic topology and microstructural material design, multiscale optimization integrates these levels simultaneously, capturing their inherent interdependencies. This integration ensures that structural performance, material distribution, and manufacturability are optimized in unison, making it particularly relevant for aerospace, automotive, and biomedical applications [157].

The origins of multiscale optimization lie in homogenization-based methods, which approximate effective macroscopic properties derived from periodic microstructures. Early work in [157] established the foundation for using homogenization in structural topology optimization, enabling the efficient coupling of scales [158]. Over time, these methods evolved to incorporate concurrent frameworks, where macrostructural and microstructural optimization variables are treated as interdependent rather than sequential. This paradigm shift has been driven by advancements in computational techniques, such as the Solid Isotropic Material with Penalization method and Discrete Material Optimization. For instance, an improved Heaviside penalization scheme was employed within a Discrete Material Optimization framework to optimize composite frame structures, concurrently varying the fiber winding angle at the microscale and cross-sectional radius at the macroscale [158]. Their results highlighted significant improvements in structural compliance compared to single scale approaches [159].

A critical innovation in multiscale optimization is its integration with additive manufacturing, which allows the fabrication of complex geometries and graded material distributions. Unlike traditional manufacturing methods that impose constraints on geometric complexity, additive manufacturing offers unprecedented design freedom. Multiscale optimization frameworks are tailored for such processes by concurrently optimizing macroscopic topology and microscopic graded microstructures in [159]. Their work on cellular composites, optimized for frequency response minimization, revealed that additive manufacturing-enabled designs achieved superior dynamic performance and manufacturability [160]. Similarly, data-driven approaches, such as Gaussian process models, were employed to integrate macro- and microscale optimization for natural frequency maximization in cellular composites [161]. By coupling computational optimization with additive manufacturing technologies, their work showcased the potential for designing multifunctional structures.

Another prominent application of multiscale optimization is in the design of dynamic and thermomechanical systems, where performance criteria such as vibration resistance, natural frequency tuning, and thermal dissipation are critical. A multiscale framework for minimizing frequency responses in graded cellular composites, leveraging parametric level-set methods to handle the coupling between scales was

Table 7
List of optimization methods for cellular structures in the recent literature.

Optimization method	Advantages	Limitations	Application
Solid isotropic material with penalization [143] 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Simple, widely used Efficient for high-resolution designs 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Can suffer from intermediate densities May lead to checkerboarding artifacts 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Cantilever beam with hexagonal lattice
Moving iso-surface threshold [144] 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Smooth geometry representation Reduces intermediate densities effectively 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Computationally intensive Challenging to control feature size directly 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Messerschmitt-Bölkow-Blohm (MBB) beam with optimized macro and microstructures
Level set method [145] 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Clear boundaries and smooth surfaces Avoids intermediate-density issues 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Requires reinitialization of the level set Sensitive to initial conditions 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Graded lattice with optimal body-centered, simple and face-centered cubic microstructures
Bi-directional evolutionary structural optimization [152] 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Intuitive, iterative material addition/removal Good for conceptual designs 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Slow convergence for large-scale problems May struggle with fine feature control 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Engine bracket with uniform lattice
Rational approximation of material properties [149] 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Smooth transitions in material distributions Better convergence compared to SIMP 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Intermediate densities can still exist More complex than SIMP to implement 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Functionally graded beam with periodic unit cell
Genetic algorithm [150] 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Capable of global optimization Handles discrete variables 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Computationally expensive Convergence can be slow and uncertain 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Optimized chiral lattice microstructure
Particle swarm [151] 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Effective for complex non-differentiable problems Suitable for global optimization 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Can suffer from premature convergence Computationally intensive for large designs 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Variable unit cells optimized for reliability

introduced in [162]. This approach demonstrated significant reductions in vibrational amplitudes, particularly for structures exposed to complex dynamic loading [160]. Furthermore, concurrent frameworks have been extended to hybrid material systems, where different reinforcement types are combined to balance strength, weight, and cost. For instance, hybrid composites were optimized by simultaneously adjusting fiber orientations and structural topology, achieving superior strength-to-weight ratios compared to conventional designs [163]. Such simultaneous procedures are illustrated in Fig. 11.

Table 9 consolidates representative quantitative outcomes from optimization-based studies across the three approaches. The compilation demonstrates that recent advances have moved well beyond conceptual or qualitative frameworks, achieving measurable performance

gains through targeted algorithmic design. For instance, variable-density and graded-cellular approaches typically report stiffness improvements exceeding 30–100 % and compliance reductions up to 25 %, while surrogate- or dynamic-driven formulations achieve frequency-response attenuation of 30–45 %. Concurrent optimization of fiber trajectories in CFCs further enhances structural efficiency, with reported strength and stiffness gains as high as 300 % over baseline designs.

Additive manufacturing will remain a cornerstone of multiscale optimization, particularly with the development of multi-material and nanoscale printing technologies. These advancements will enable the fabrication of non-periodic, hierarchical designs that were previously infeasible [184]. Furthermore, as sustainability becomes a critical consideration, multiscale optimization will need to incorporate metrics

Table 8
List of fiber-orientation optimization methods for cellular structures in the recent literature.

Optimization method	Advantages	Limitations	Application
Continuous fiber angle optimization [153]	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Allows smooth variation in fiber orientation Improves strength and stiffness along optimal load paths 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Computationally intensive Requires complex manufacturing processes 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Laminated composite cylindrical tube – fiber volume fraction
 Discrete material optimization [154]	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Simplifies manufacturing with discrete fiber orientations Efficient for capturing distinct load paths 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Complexity of controlling the printing parameters 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Gripper design with optimal fiber directions
 Stress lines method [155]	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Aligns fibers along principal stress lines for efficient load-bearing Reduces material usage 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Dependent on accurate stress field estimation May not capture complex load cases well 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> MBB beam with principal stress trajectories

Fig. 11. Concurrent optimization at two scales, simultaneously accounting for fiber orientations, connectivity and printing path.

for material efficiency, recyclability, and environmental impact. Researchers are beginning to explore the use of bio-inspired and natural materials, which could play a significant role in future designs [185].

4. Challenges & limitations

Despite deep knowledge of the mechanical behaviour and manufacturing of CFCs which has been obtained during recent years, there are still open horizons that need to be fulfilled within future research. To gain efficient cellular structures with incredible features, a profound understanding of the mechanical/thermal behaviours of the CFCs is essential. For this purpose, the following challenges must be resolved as stated in Table 10.

5. Conclusion & outlook

5.1. Summary

CFCs represent a transformative approach to achieving lightweight, high-strength, and multifunctional materials for advanced engineering applications. While challenges remain in material compatibility, manufacturing precision, scalability, and environmental sustainability, ongoing advancements in additive manufacturing, computational design tools, and smart materials are driving innovative solutions. Addressing critical aspects such as dynamic performance consistency, defect management, and eco-friendly manufacturing processes will unlock their full potential across industries. Future research directions in composite cellular structures extend beyond conventional material design, integrating quantum materials, intelligent composites, and next-generation adaptive systems. The development of quantum-enhanced cellular architectures, with precise control over electronic states and tunable dielectric properties, opens new frontiers for material

Table 9
Quantitative comparison of optimization methods applied to CFCSS, grouped by cellular, fiber-orientation, and multiscale concurrent design frameworks.

Method	Objective(s)	Outcomes	Validation
Cellular optimization			
Density-based TO [164]	Max stiffness/strength for AM parts	Stiffness ↑110 %, Strength ↑75 %	Printed beam tests
Meta-model (Kriging/RSM) [165]	Max energy absorption, limit peak force	SEA ↑1.07 % (Q-RSM), ↑1.04 % (Kriging)	LS-DYNA validation
Multi-scale SIMP + Level-set [166]	Minimize compliance	Compliance ↓15.5 %	Numerical
Analytical + FE [167]	Optimize joint thickness	Stiffness ↑37.8 %, Peak stress ↓	3D-printed tests
Adaptive concurrent TO [168]	Macro–micro shape optimization	Cost ↓20 %	Numerical
Dynamic multiscale TO [169]	Min dynamic compliance	Response ↓30 %	Benchmarks
Multiscale TO + Kriging [170]	Min frequency response	Response ↓35–45 %	Numerical
BESO + inverse homogenization [171]	Max bulk/shear moduli	$E_{eff}/E_s \approx 0.4–0.6$	FE homogenization
Fiber-orientation optimization			
Sequential fiber + TO [172]	Minimize compliance	Compliance ↓15–20 %	Numerical
Gradient + filtered orientation [173]	Minimize compliance	Stiffness ↑20 %	Printed CF samples
TO + fiber path opt. [38]	Max stiffness, min mass	Spec. stiffness ↑100 %, Weight ↓50 %	Experimental (DIC)
Sequential SIMP + path tracing [170]	Max strength/stiffness	Strength ↑305 %, Stiffness ↑256 %	Printed CF samples
Fiber path in diamond lattices [38]	Max tensile properties	↑ tensile strength with fiber volume	Tensile tests
GA laminate optimization [174]	Max stiffness/strength	Stiffness ↑25 %, Strength ↑20 %, Weight ↓10 %	FE+ tests
GA for natural fiber composite [175]	Max tensile/flexural	Tensile ↑18 %, Flexural ↑26 %	Experimental
Concurrent TO + fiber path [176]	Optimize stiffness+ peak load	MBB: +36 %/+64 %; Cantilever: +123 %/+52 %	Experimental
Multiscale concurrent optimization			
Layered level-set multiscale TO [177]	Tailor FG composites	Compliance ↓15 %	Numerical
Robust TO under hybrid uncertainties [178]	Minimize variance of compliance	Response variance ↓25 %	Numerical
DMO-based multiscale TO [179]	Max natural freq	Freq ↑20 %	Benchmarks
Data-driven multiscale [180]	Max freq	Freq ↑25 %	Numerical
Multi-material multiscale TO [181]	Min compliance	Mass ↓10 %, anisotropy tailored	Numerical
Heaviside penalized two-scale [182]	Min compliance	Ultra-light design	Numerical
Dynamic multiscale [169]	Min dynamic compliance	Response ↓30 %	2D/3D FE
Graded microstructure multiscale [170]	Min frequency response	Response ↓35–45 %	Numerical
Multiscale graded microstructures [183]	Min compliance	Stiffness ↑25 %	FE

Table 10
List of remaining challenges in the field of CFCSS.

Domain	Name	Description
Modelling/simulation	Material modelling	<p>Anisotropic behaviour: Continuous fiber composites are highly anisotropic, and capturing their directional properties requires detailed material models [186].</p> <p>Interfacial behaviour: The interaction between fibers and the matrix needs precise representation, especially under dynamic loading or complex stress states [187,188].</p> <p>Multiscale nature: Simulations must account for behaviour at multiple scales, from the microscale (fiber-matrix interaction) to the macroscale (overall structural performance) [189–192].</p> <p>Fiber misalignment: Real-world deviations in fiber placement can significantly affect performance but are hard to incorporate into simulations [193].</p> <p>Residual stresses: Stresses induced during fabrication, such as curing or thermal gradients, are challenging to predict and include in models [194].</p> <p>Porosity and defects: Manufacturing processes may introduce voids or defects that alter mechanical properties and are difficult to quantify [195–197].</p> <p>Damage and failure mechanisms: CFCSS exhibit complex failure modes, including fiber breakage, delamination, and matrix cracking, which are computationally expensive to simulate [198–200].</p> <p>Large deformations: Under certain load conditions, cellular structures may undergo significant deformations, requiring advanced nonlinear solvers [201–203].</p> <p>Dynamic loading: High-frequency or impact loading scenarios demand advanced time-dependent analyses, which are computationally intensive [204–206].</p> <p>Environmental conditions: Exposure to temperature, humidity, or chemical agents alters material behavior, necessitating coupled field analyses [207–209].</p> <p>High computational cost: Fine meshes, multiscale models, and advanced material laws significantly increase simulation time and hardware requirements [208,210].</p> <p>Convergence issues: Nonlinear analyses and complex boundary conditions often lead to convergence problems in numerical solvers.</p> <p>Inadequate built-in models: Many commercial software packages lack dedicated modules for cellular composites with continuous fibers, necessitating custom scripting or plugins [211].</p> <p>Integration with manufacturing models: Bridging the gap between CAD designs, manufacturing process simulations, and structural analyses remains challenging.</p> <p>Fiber-matrix compatibility: Ensuring proper bonding between continuous fibers and the matrix</p>
	Manufacturing-induced effects	<p>Nonlinear behaviour</p> <p>Dynamic and environmental effects</p> <p>Software limitations</p>
Manufacturing	Material challenges	

(continued on next page)

Table 10 (continued)

Domain	Name	Description
Process limitations		material is critical but challenging, especially with thermosets [31]. Fiber impregnation: Achieving uniform resin distribution along fibers is complex, particularly for intricate cellular designs [212].
		Complex geometries: Producing intricate cellular structures with continuous fibers requires precise control of the deposition process to avoid defects like fiber misalignment or voids [208,213]. Fabricating rate: Printing with continuous fibers is slower compared to traditional 3D printing processes, limiting scalability for large structures [71,96,97,214]. Trajectory generation: Generating optimal trajectory for continuous fibers in cellular geometries is challenging and computationally intensive [193,199,213,215,216].
		Real-time quality control: Monitoring fiber alignment, deposition rate, and material flow in real-time is challenging [193,199, 216]. Repeatability: Achieving consistent results across multiple builds remains difficult due to process variability [217–219].
Process monitoring and control		Fiber continuity: Ensuring continuous fiber paths throughout the structure without breaks or overlaps is difficult, particularly in complex geometries [220]. Defect management: Issues such as porosity, voids, or delamination can occur during printing, reducing mechanical performance [56,196, 221]. Residual stress: Thermal gradients during the printing process can introduce residual stresses, affecting dimensional accuracy and mechanical properties [133,222].
Structural integrity		Multiscale computing: Handling optimisation across two scales (macroscopic and microscopic) significantly increases computational demands [157,158]. Iterative computing: Evaluating the effective material properties at each design iteration, especially for complex microstructures or large design domains, can be computationally expensive [159].
Optimization	Computational cost	Constitutive models: Capturing the nonlinear anisotropic behaviour of continuous fiber composites under large deformations or failure conditions, requires sophisticated constitutive models [160]. Multiscale behaviours: Interaction between fibers and matrix at the microscale and translate that behaviour to the macroscale [161].
		Manufacturing-related issues: Many optimisation algorithms do not consider the specific constraints imposed by manufacturing processes, such as limitations on fiber curvature, minimum printable features, or the achievable resolution of fiber placement [162]. Ideal designs: Failure to incorporate
	Material modelling	
	Manufacturing constraints	

Table 10 (continued)

Domain	Name	Description
	Connectivity of microstructures	these constraints during the design phase can lead to designs that are impractical or impossible to manufacture [163]. Connections between microstructures: In cases where the microstructure is allowed to vary spatially, ensuring smooth transitions and connections between different microstructural regions poses a significant challenge [185]. Stress concentrations: Abrupt changes in fiber orientation or volume fraction at the boundaries between adjacent microstructures can lead to stress concentrations reducing the overall structural integrity [223].

performance. At the same time, the incorporation of AI-driven generative design and real-time digital twins will lead to unprecedented levels of optimization and predictive maintenance. Advanced fabrication techniques, including multi-material 3D printing, and 4D printing, promise structures with dynamic adaptability, while hybrid additive-subtractive methods will ensure consistency in industrial-scale production. Industrial integration remains a crucial step, with scalable manufacturing methods such as automated fiber placement and in-line quality control ensuring high-performance, cost-effective solutions. Expanded applications in soft robotics, aerospace, and renewable energy sectors highlight the versatility of these materials, with examples such as wind turbine blades featuring 3D-printed cellular cores for enhanced efficiency and sustainability.

Moreover, research into the electrical conductivity of cellular composites, the development of environmentally adaptable materials, and improved structural stability under extreme conditions will further broaden their applicability. A strong emphasis on sustainability is shaping the future of cellular composites. Closed-loop manufacturing systems, recyclable matrices, and bioinspired materials will reduce environmental impact and align with global sustainability goals. Additionally, new applications in energy absorption, morphing structures, advanced vibration isolators, biomechanical devices, and electromagnetic shielding showcase the vast potential of these materials. Integration with smart sensing technologies and multi-source energy harvesting systems will further enhance their functionality in critical industries [224]. As research continues to bridge the gap between theoretical design and practical implementation, composite cellular structures are poised to revolutionize sectors such as aerospace, automotive, marine, and biomedical engineering. By embracing a multidisciplinary approach that merges materials science, computational intelligence, and advanced manufacturing, these structures will play a key role in advancing sustainable and high-performance technologies, paving the way for groundbreaking engineering solutions in the years to come.

5.2. Future perspectives and applications

5.2.1. Future perspectives

CFCs are positioned to revolutionize material applications across diverse industries. By addressing beforementioned limitations and integrating the following novel functionalities through advanced materials, design innovations, and cutting-edge manufacturing technologies, these structures are poised to redefine the boundaries of engineering and performance:

- **Next-generation materials:** The integration of smart and adaptive materials within cellular composites represents a transformative opportunity [225]. Materials such as shape-memory alloys [226],

piezoelectric elements [227], and self-healing composites [228] will enable real-time adaptability, enhanced durability, and resilience under extreme conditions. Additionally, the rise of biocompatible and sustainable materials, driven by environmental priorities, paves the way for applications in medicine [229], consumer goods [230], and eco-conscious engineering solutions [231].

(1) *Quantum-driven cellular composite structure*: Moving beyond these emerging directions, an even more advanced frontier lies in quantum-level approaches to engineering CFCs. This convergence of quantum physics and materials science opens new pathways beyond conventional limitations. Following this quantum-focused direction, three key research frontiers emerge in the design of intelligent composite materials:

a. *Precise control of electronic states in CFCs at micro- and nano-scale*: Harness the unique electronic and spin properties of topological insulators and advanced quantum materials. Employ micro-nanofabrication techniques to fine-tune the unit structures of CFCs, enabling precise control of electronic states within each unit. This approach aims to significantly enhance overall dielectric properties and functional performance.

b. *Development of quantum materials with spin-charge coupling to optimize CFCs*: Design and synthesize spin-charge coupled quantum materials and integrate them into CFCs. This integration expands the functional degrees of freedom, enables highly efficient and programmable dielectric performance, and enhances intelligent responses and the multifunctional potential of the structures.

c. *Building cross-scale correlation models between quantum states and macroscopic properties of CFCs*: Develop multiscale theoretical frameworks and numerical simulation methods to establish a connection between quantum state behaviors and the macroscopic dielectric properties of CFCs. This approach seeks to predict and optimize material performance, ensuring that microscopic quantum effects are effectively translated into macroscopic enhancements.

(2) *Electrical conductivity of CFCs*: Future research directions could delve into the electrical conductivity of CFCs, focusing on the following areas:

a. *Electrical properties*: Enhanced electrical properties in CFCs may be accessible through the incorporation of conductive materials, such as 2D nanomaterials or other advanced materials [232].

b. *Influence on electrical conductivity*: Investigation of how various structural designs affect conductivity, with particular emphasis on the effects of porosity [232], structural orientation [233], and interfacial properties on overall electrical performance.

c. *Tunable electrical conductivity*: Development of smart composite materials with tunable electrical conductivity [234]. By carefully designing structures and compositions, dynamic modulation of electrical properties can be achieved, paving the way for innovative material solutions in advanced electronics, sensing technologies, and energy applications.

- **Advanced design paradigms**: The application of generative design and AI-driven optimization will lead to novel cellular architectures that perfectly balance structural and functional requirements [235]. Integrating digital twins, i.e., virtual replicas of physical systems, will allow for real-time monitoring, predictive maintenance, and unparalleled reliability [236,237]. These advancements will extend the lifespan of cellular composites in demanding environments.
- **Innovative manufacturing and scalable production**: Emerging fabrication technologies are advancing the intelligent manufacturing of cellular composites. Techniques like multi-material 3D printing [238], voxel-level control [239], and 4D printing [240] enable structures with graded properties and dynamic responses [241]. AI and robotics can enhance scalability and precision [242], while hybrid additive-subtractive methods improve industrial consistency and quality [243]. This is especially pertinent within the context of

multiphase structures [244]. However, scaling these capabilities for mass production relies on innovations like automated fiber placement [245] and in-line quality control to ensure the performance of complex structures. Bridging the lab-to-industry gap is thus key to the widespread adoption of these advanced materials.

- **Expanded applications**: The tailored properties and multifunctionality of these composites will unlock applications in emerging fields like soft robotics [246], aerospace reentry systems [247], and renewable energy infrastructure [248]. For example, wind turbine blades featuring 3D-printed cellular cores can achieve superior efficiency and sustainability [249], while smart morphing materials [250] could optimize spacecraft and autonomous vehicles for dynamic environments.
- **Structural stability**: The structural stability of materials under extreme conditions, including high temperatures [251], low temperatures [252], and high pressures [253] must be investigated to ensure structural integrity and functional performance in harsh environments. Moreover, the development of durable and environmentally adaptive composite materials is crucial for extending the service life and expanding the operational envelope of CFCs [254, 255]. Improving the environmental adaptability of these systems can further diversify their potential applications, which can be discussed in terms of the following two key aspects:

1. **Structural stability**: Investigate the structural stability of materials under extreme conditions, including hot/cold temperatures, high pressures, to ensure structural integrity and functional performance in harsh environments.

2. **Adaptable**: Develop durable and environmentally adaptable composite materials to extend the lifespan and broaden the application scope of CFCs in extreme environments.

- **Environmental sustainability**: Sustainability will be a defining aspect of future cellular composites [250]. Developing closed-loop manufacturing systems and fully recyclable matrices will significantly reduce environmental impact [256]. Efforts to reuse and repurpose materials at the end of their lifecycle will align with global sustainability goals, ensuring that these advancements contribute to a greener future [257].

5.2.2. Key applications

Considering the growing demand for materials that combine load-bearing capacity with active system regulation, cellular composites are set to redefine multiple application domains. Their tunable micro-architectures and hybrid material combinations enable not only exceptional mechanical performance but also dynamic responses to thermal, environmental, and mechanical stimuli. By exploiting these features, forthcoming research will translate design innovations into practical technologies across a diverse spectrum of fields. A summary of the prospective key application areas of CFCs is provided below.

- **Thermal insulators**: Thermal management is a critical area where CFCs can make transformative contributions. By incorporating adaptive thermal management systems, such as phase-change materials [258] and thermoelectric elements [259], future composites can achieve dynamic heat regulation tailored to specific operating environments. For example, in aerospace applications, these materials could mitigate extreme temperature fluctuations by storing and releasing thermal energy, enhancing the performance and lifespan of sensitive electronic and mechanical systems [260]. In cryogenic environments, advanced composites can maintain stability and efficiency by reducing thermal gradients [261]. To address the challenge of anisotropic thermal properties, where heat transfer differs along various material directions [262], AI-driven optimization techniques can be employed to design isotropic or controlled anisotropic behaviors tailored to the application [263]. These

methods allow for precise control of thermal conductivity across complex geometries, ensuring consistent performance. The integration of multifunctional layers combining thermal insulation with structural integrity further enhances their utility in high-demand industries, such as energy, defense [264], and space exploration [265].

- Fog harvesting:** The scarcity of freshwater resources in many parts of the world has driven innovation in fog-harvesting technologies [266], where cellular composites can play a pivotal role. Future advancements will feature multifunctional surfaces inspired by nature, such as the Namib Desert beetle, which has evolved to collect water efficiently in arid environments. By mimicking these biological systems, researchers can develop nanostructured surfaces capable of trapping and channeling water droplets with minimal losses [267]. These surfaces can combine self-cleaning properties to maintain efficiency in polluted or dusty environments and anti-fouling characteristics to prevent biological contamination. Self-healing coatings [268], enhanced with wear-resistant materials, will ensure durability under prolonged exposure to ultraviolet light and harsh weather conditions, extending the operational lifespan of fog-harvesting systems. Potential applications range from providing water in remote or desert regions to enhancing industrial cooling systems and sustainable urban infrastructure.
- Advanced vibration isolators:** Vibration control is crucial in aerospace [269], automotive [270], and industrial applications [271], where dynamic loads can significantly impact performance and safety. Cellular composites embedded with smart damping systems, such as piezoelectric or magnetorheological materials, enable real-time adaptability by actively responding to changes in frequency or load [272]. For example, in aerospace applications, these systems can counteract high-frequency vibrations caused by turbulent airflow or mechanical operation [273], protecting critical components. Hybrid materials combining viscoelastic matrices with high-damping fibers provide an additional layer of vibration attenuation [274]. These materials ensure consistent performance over a wide range of frequencies and operating conditions, making them suitable for sensitive machinery and structural applications [275]. By integrating sensors and AI-based controllers, these systems can also enable predictive maintenance, identifying potential failures before they occur, thereby reducing downtime and repair costs [276].
- Morphing structures:** Breakthroughs in 4D printing, where materials change shape or function over time in response to external stimuli [277] are paving the way for morphing cellular composites. These structures can adapt to environmental changes such as temperature fluctuations [278], electromagnetic fields [279], or mechanical stress [280], making them ideal for aerospace, automotive, and defense applications. One of the primary challenges in morphing structures is fatigue resistance under cyclic loading, as repeated shape changes can degrade material performance [281]. Bioinspired designs, such as those modeled after the stress-distribution patterns in bone or plant stems, can evenly distribute stress and reduce fatigue [282]. Additionally, incorporating self-healing materials that repair microscopic cracks and defects will further enhance durability. These advancements open up possibilities for applications like adaptive airfoils [283], deployable satellite structures [284], and reconfigurable robotics [285].
- Advanced civil structures:** Cellular composites are set to revolutionize civil engineering by enabling lightweight [286], and modular construction [287] that maintains high mechanical performance. By combining hybrid manufacturing methods, such as additive manufacturing and automated fiber placement, with AI-driven design optimization, engineers can create customized components for bridges, skyscrapers, and energy-efficient walls [288]. These materials also offer integrated sensor networks for real-time structural health monitoring. For example, bridges constructed with cellular composites [289] can detect and report stress, cracks, or other issues, allowing for proactive maintenance and enhanced safety. Furthermore, the modularity of these structures facilitates rapid assembly and disassembly, reducing construction times, and enabling more sustainable infrastructure development [290].
- Energy absorption:** Tailored energy absorption is critical for improving crashworthiness in the automotive, aerospace, and defense sectors [291]. Cellular composites with graded architectures can achieve precise control over deformation mechanisms. These structures can dissipate energy more effectively during impact, minimizing damage to occupants or critical equipment. In particular, the incorporation of non-Newtonian fillers has been shown to significantly enhance the impact resistance, especially under low-velocity impact loading [292]. The use of auxetic materials, which exhibit a negative Poisson's ratio, further enhances energy absorption by allowing the material to expand laterally under compression [293]. Multi-material additive manufacturing provides the ability to fabricate such complex geometries with a high degree of accuracy, ensuring performance consistency [294]. Applications extend beyond crash protection to include energy-absorbing barriers, protective sports gear, and shock-isolating infrastructure [295].
- Biomechanics applications:** The development of biomechanical devices, such as bone scaffolds and prosthetics, is another promising application for cellular composites [296]. These materials can mimic the hierarchical structure and functionality of biological tissues, offering a combination of bioactivity and mechanical strength. By integrating bioactive phases with cellular architectures, researchers can promote bone regeneration and osseointegration in implants. 3D bioprinting and AI-driven personalization will enable the creation of patient-specific medical devices. For example, scaffolds tailored to the patient's anatomy can accelerate healing and reduce complications in load-bearing applications, such as spinal implants or joint replacements. Moreover, the incorporation of regenerative materials can extend the functional lifespan of these devices, reducing the need for replacements or additional surgeries [297].
- Sensors applications:** The integration of flexible and stretchable sensors into cellular composites transforms them into smart systems capable of real-time monitoring [298]. These sensors can detect parameters like stress, temperature, and environmental conditions in some wide ranges, making them invaluable for structural health monitoring and wearable technologies. Advanced encapsulation techniques will protect these sensors from mechanical damage, moisture, and other environmental factors, ensuring long-term reliability [299]. Additionally, the development of self-powered sensor systems, such as those based on piezoelectric or triboelectric mechanisms, will reduce the need for external power sources, expanding their applicability in remote or challenging environments [300].
- New generation of energy harvesters:** Cellular composites incorporating piezoelectric [301], triboelectric [302], and thermoelectric materials [303] offer the potential for multi-source energy harvesting. These systems can capture energy from mechanical vibrations [304], thermal gradients [305], and environmental stress [305], converting it into usable electricity. By engineering the fiber-matrix interface at the nanoscale, researchers can enhance mechanical-electrical coupling efficiency [306], maximizing energy output. Self-healing technologies will address durability challenges [307], ensuring consistent performance over extended periods. These advancements are critical for powering remote sensors, wearable devices, and other applications requiring sustainable, low-maintenance energy solutions.
- Electromagnetic shielding:** CFCs exhibit outstanding potential in the domain of electromagnetic shielding materials [308–313]. By precisely engineering multilayer honeycomb-like microstructures, CFCs achieve broadband, highly efficient electromagnetic wave attenuation [314]. The integration of conductive fillers such as graphene [315] and carbon nanotubes [316] ensures not only

lightweight properties but also a significant enhancement in shielding performance. This innovative structure is particularly well-suited for applications in 5G communication [317–319], electromagnetic interference resistance in electronic devices [320], and military electronic countermeasure systems [321], marking the forefront of electromagnetic protection technology.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Amin Farrokhbadi: Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Supervision, Investigation, Formal analysis, Conceptualization. **Houyu Lu:** Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis. **Abhilash Sreekumar:** Writing – original draft, Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation. **Mohammad Mahdi Ashrafiyan:** Software, Investigation, Formal analysis. **Dimitrios Chronopoulos:** Writing – original draft, Software, Project administration, Conceptualization.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

References

- [1] M.F. Ashby, The properties of foams and lattices, *Philos. Trans. R. Soc. A: Math. Phys. Eng. Sci.* 364 (1838) (2006) 15–30.
- [2] M.F. Ashby, L.J. Gibson, *Cellular Solids: Structure And Properties*, Press Syndicate of the University of Cambridge, Cambridge, UK, 1997, pp. 175–231.
- [3] A. Nazir, et al., A state-of-the-art review on types, design, optimization, and additive manufacturing of cellular structures, *Int. J. Adv. Manuf. Technol.* 104 (2019) 3489–3510.
- [4] A. Pais, J. Belinha, J. Alves, Advances in computational techniques for bio-inspired cellular materials in the field of biomechanics: current trends and prospects, *Materials* 16 (11) (2023) 3946.
- [5] C. Pan, Y. Han, J. Lu, Design and optimization of lattice structures: a review, *Appl. Sci.* 10 (18) (2020) 6374.
- [6] N. Khan, A. Riccio, A systematic review of design for additive manufacturing of aerospace lattice structures: current trends and future directions, *Prog. Aerosp. Sci.* 149 (2024) 101021.
- [7] I.G. Ian Gibson, *Additive Manufacturing Technologies 3D Printing, Rapid Prototyping, And Direct Digital Manufacturing*, Springer, 2015.
- [8] F. Czerwinski, Current trends in automotive lightweighting strategies and materials, *Materials* 14 (21) (2021) 6631.
- [9] M.Y. Kondo, et al., Recent advances in the use of Polyamide-based materials for the automotive industry, *Polímeros* 32 (2) (2022) e2022023.
- [10] A. Praveen Kumar, et al., Static axial crushing response on the energy absorption capability of hybrid Kenaf/Glass fabric cylindrical tubes, *Mater. Today: Proc.* 27 (2020) 783–787.
- [11] Q. Ma, et al., Axial and radial crushing behaviour of thin-walled carbon fiber-reinforced polymer tubes fabricated by the real-time winding angle measurement system, *Forces Mech.* 10 (2023) 100170.
- [12] P.K. Alagesan, et al., Comparison of the lateral crushing response of thin-walled aluminum-thermoplastic polymer composite cylindrical shells, *Mech. Adv. Mater. Struct.* 32 (16) (2025) 3939–3954.
- [13] S.K. Hedayati, et al., 3D printed PCL scaffold reinforced with continuous biodegradable fiber yarn: a study on mechanical and cell viability properties, *Polym. Test.* 83 (2020) 106347.
- [14] Y. Zhang, et al., Polymer fiber scaffolds for bone and cartilage tissue engineering, *Adv. Funct. Mater.* 29 (36) (2019) 1903279.
- [15] C. Rendenbach, et al., Patient specific glass fiber reinforced composite versus titanium plate: A comparative biomechanical analysis under cyclic dynamic loading, *J. Mech. Behav. Biomed. Mater.* 91 (2019) 212–219.
- [16] F. Rubino, et al., Marine application of fiber reinforced composites: a review, *J. Mar. Sci. Eng.* 8 (1) (2020) 26.
- [17] L. Chica, A. Alzate, Cellular concrete review: new trends for application in construction, *Constr. Build. Mater.* 200 (2019) 637–647.
- [18] M. Avarzamani, et al., Energy absorption response of functionally graded 3D printed continuous fiber reinforced composite cellular structures: experimental and numerical approaches, *Mech. Adv. Mater. Struct.* 32 (4) (2025) 538–554.
- [19] S. Alkunte, et al., Functionally graded metamaterials: fabrication techniques, modeling, and applications—a review, *Processes* 12 (2024), <https://doi.org/10.3390/pr12102252>.
- [20] I.M. Hassan, et al., The mechanical performance of functionally graded Schwarz primitive and Schoen-IWP cellular structures fabricated by additive manufacturing, *Prog. Addit. Manuf.* 8 (2) (2023) 303–311.
- [21] J. Zhou, et al., Energy absorption of auxetic honeycomb with graded beam thickness based on Bezier curve, *Aerosp. Sci. Technol.* 155 (2024) 109619.
- [22] R. Doodi, B.M. Gunji, An experimental and numerical investigation on the performance of novel hybrid bio-inspired 3D printed lattice structures for stiffness and energy absorption applications, *Mech. Adv. Mater. Struct.* 31 (17) (2024) 3970–3979.
- [23] F. Ghorbani, et al., Investigation of energy absorption performances of a 3D printed fiber-reinforced bio-inspired cellular structure under in-plane compression loading, *Mech. Adv. Mater. Struct.* 31 (21) (2024) 5234–5252.
- [24] P. Wang, et al., Bio-inspired multi-cell tubular structures approaching ideal energy absorption performance, *Mater. Des.* 225 (2023) 111495.
- [25] J. Song, et al., Bamboo-inspired hierarchical microlattice structures (BHMSs) for high strength and energy absorption, *Mech. Adv. Mater. Struct.* 31 (26) (2024) 7991–8003.
- [26] H. Yin, et al., Optimization design of a novel hybrid hierarchical cellular structure for crashworthiness, *Compos. Struct.* 303 (2023) 116335.
- [27] S. Zhang, et al., 3D printing thermoplastic polyurethane hierarchical cellular foam with outstanding energy absorption capability, *Addit. Manuf.* 76 (2023) 103770.
- [28] J. Li, et al., An efficient deep learning-based topology optimization method for continuous fiber composite structure, *Acta Mech. Sin.* 41 (4) (2024) 424207.
- [29] C. Luo, et al., Design, manufacturing and applications of auxetic tubular structures: a review, *Thin-Walled Struct.* 163 (2021) 107682.
- [30] S.F. Kabir, K. Mathur, A.-F.M. Seyam, A critical review on 3D printed continuous fiber-reinforced composites: history, mechanism, materials and properties, *Compos. Struct.* 232 (2020) 111476.
- [31] R.F. Gibson, A review of recent research on mechanics of multifunctional composite materials and structures, *Compos. Struct.* 92 (12) (2010) 2793–2810.
- [32] Z. Hou, et al., 3D printed continuous fibre reinforced composite corrugated structure, *Compos. Struct.* 184 (2018) 1005–1010.
- [33] S. Liu, Y. Li, N. Li, A novel free-hanging 3D printing method for continuous carbon fiber reinforced thermoplastic lattice truss core structures, *Mater. Des.* 137 (2018) 235–244.
- [34] H. Jishi, R. Umer, W. Cantwell, The fabrication and mechanical properties of novel composite lattice structures, *Mater. Des.* 91 (2016) 286–293.
- [35] T. George, V.S. Deshpande, H.N. Wadley, Mechanical response of carbon fiber composite sandwich panels with pyramidal truss cores, *Compos. A: Appl. Sci. Manuf.* 47 (2013) 31–40.
- [36] B. Wang, et al., Mechanical behavior of the sandwich structures with carbon fiber-reinforced pyramidal lattice truss core, *Mater. Des.* (1980-2015) 31 (5) (2010) 2659–2663.
- [37] A.V. Azarov, et al., Composite 3D printing for the small size unmanned aerial vehicle structure, *Compos. B: Eng.* 169 (2019) 157–163.
- [38] K. Dong, et al., 3D printing of continuous fiber reinforced diamond cellular structural composites and tensile properties, *Compos. Struct.* 250 (2020) 112610.
- [39] E. Giarmas, et al., Mechanical and FEA-assisted characterization of 3D printed continuous glass fiber reinforced nylon cellular structures, *J. Compos. Sci.* 5 (2021), <https://doi.org/10.3390/jcs5120313>.
- [40] M. Kepenekci, et al., Mechanical performance of carbon fiber-reinforced polymer cellular structures manufactured via fused filament fabrication, *Polym. Compos.* 44 (8) (2023) 4654–4668.
- [41] B. Szederkényi, N.K. Kovács, T. Czigan, Improving energy absorption in cellular 3D-printed fiber-reinforced structures with radially reinforced composite shells, *Compos. B: Eng.* 301 (2025) 112513.
- [42] Q. Chen, et al., Embedded 3D printing of isotropically enhanced lattice structure with programmable elasticity via three-dimensional fiber alignment, *Addit. Manuf.* 105 (2025) 104783.
- [43] C. Yang, et al., 3D printing for continuous fiber reinforced thermoplastic composites: mechanism and performance, *Rapid Prototyp. J.* 23 (1) (2017) 209–215.
- [44] Z. Liu, et al., A critical review of fused deposition modeling 3D printing technology in manufacturing polylactic acid parts, *Int. J. Adv. Manuf. Technol.* 102 (2019) 2877–2889.
- [45] R. Matsuzaki, et al., Three-dimensional printing of continuous-fiber composites by in-nozzle impregnation, *Sci. Rep.* 6 (1) (2016) 23058.
- [46] H.-J. Um, et al., 3D printed continuous carbon fiber reinforced thermoplastic composite sandwich structure with corrugated core for high stiffness/load capability, *Compos. Struct.* 291 (2022) 115590.
- [47] C. Quan, et al., 3d printed continuous fiber reinforced composite auxetic honeycomb structures, *Compos. B: Eng.* 187 (2020) 107858.
- [48] T. Cersoli, et al., 3D printing of a continuous fiber-reinforced composite based on a coaxial Kevlar/PLA filament, *Compos. Adv. Mater.* 30 (2021), 26349833211000058.
- [49] K. Sugiyama, et al., 3D printing of composite sandwich structures using continuous carbon fiber and fiber tension, *Compos. A: Appl. Sci. Manuf.* 113 (2018) 114–121.
- [50] J. Zhang, et al., Fused deposition modeling 3D printing of continuous natural and regeneration fibers reinforced polymer composites and its mechanical properties under extreme environmental conditions—a critical review, *BioResources* 20 (2) (2025) 4877–4896.
- [51] J. Zhou, et al., Comparison of different quasi-static loading conditions of additively manufactured composite hexagonal and auxetic cellular structures, *Int. J. Mech. Sci.* 244 (2023) 108054.

- [52] D. Christianto, D. Kurniadi, Effect of steel fiber on the shear strength of reactive powder concrete, in: IOP Conference Series: Materials Science and Engineering, IOP Publishing, 2019.
- [53] K. Dong, et al., Mechanical properties and shape memory effect of 4D printed cellular structure composite with a novel continuous fiber-reinforced printing path, *Mater. Des.* 198 (2021) 109303.
- [54] K. Mathur, S.F. Kabir, A.-F.M. Seyam, Tensile properties of 3D printed continuous fiberglass reinforced cellular composites, *J. Text. Inst.* 113 (1) (2022) 60–69.
- [55] R. Guerra Silva, G.M. Pavez, Flexural characteristics of additively manufactured continuous fiber-reinforced honeycomb sandwich structures, *Compos. C: Open Access* 16 (2025) 100563.
- [56] Q. He, et al., 3D printed continuous CF/PA6 composites: effect of microscopic voids on mechanical performance, *Compos. Sci. Technol.* 191 (2020) 108077.
- [57] J. Hu, 3-D Fibrous Assemblies: Properties, Applications and Modelling of Three-Dimensional Textile Structures, Elsevier, 2008.
- [58] F.A. Ibitoye, D.W. Radford, Additive manufacturing of sandwich panels with continuous fiber reinforced high modulus composite facings, *Polym. Compos.* 46 (4) (2025) 3636–3654.
- [59] Y. Ming, et al., Investigation on process parameters of 3D printed continuous carbon fiber-reinforced thermosetting epoxy composites, *Addit. Manuf.* 33 (2020) 101184.
- [60] C. Zeng, et al., Compression behavior and energy absorption of 3D printed continuous fiber reinforced composite honeycomb structures with shape memory effects, *Addit. Manuf.* 38 (2021) 101842.
- [61] K. Dong, et al., Reusability and energy absorption behavior of 4D printed continuous fiber-reinforced auxetic composite structures, *Compos. A: Appl. Sci. Manuf.* 169 (2023) 107529.
- [62] Y. Wang, et al., Fabrication strategy for joints in 3D printed continuous fiber reinforced composite lattice structures, *Compos. Commun.* 30 (2022) 101080.
- [63] N. Wei, Y. Rao, A process-driven evaluation strategy for mechanical performances of additively manufactured short-fiber reinforced polymer structures, *Constr. Build. Mater.* 463 (2025) 140023.
- [64] J. Xiang, et al., Effects of undulating printing paths on axial compressive behaviors of 3D-printed continuous fiber-reinforced multi-cell thin-walled structure, *Eng. Struct.* 325 (2025) 119353.
- [65] M.M. Ashrafi, A. Farrokhhabadi, M. Avarzamani, Energy absorption of a composite sandwich panel with 3D printed unbalanced/balanced configuration morphing core, *Polym. Compos.* 46 (14) (2025) 13123–13138.
- [66] X. Li, et al., Enhanced mechanical properties of sandwich panels via integrated 3D printing of continuous fiber face sheet and TPMS core, *Thin-Walled Struct.* 204 (2024) 112312.
- [67] Z. Zhai, et al., Novel sandwich structures with double-row and crossed pyramidal lattice cores: design, fabrication and bending behavior, *Eng. Fail. Anal.* 170 (2025) 109267.
- [68] S. Wang, et al., Bending performance and failure modes of sinusoidal corrugated sandwich panels fabricated using stereolithography technology: effects of geometric parameters, *Eng. Fail. Anal.* 158 (2024) 107987.
- [69] Y. Chen, L. Ye, Designing and tailoring effective elastic modulus and negative Poisson's ratio with continuous carbon fibres using 3D printing, *Compos. A: Appl. Sci. Manuf.* 150 (2021) 106625.
- [70] Y. Cheng, et al., 3D printed recoverable honeycomb composites reinforced by continuous carbon fibers, *Compos. Struct.* 268 (2021) 113974.
- [71] A. Farrokhhabadi, et al., Evaluation of the equivalent mechanical properties in a novel composite cruciform honeycomb using analytical and numerical methods, *Compos. Struct.* 275 (2021) 114410.
- [72] W. Hao, et al., Failure analysis of 3D printed glass fiber/PA12 composite lattice structures using DIC, *Compos. Struct.* 225 (2019) 111192.
- [73] M. Saleh, et al., Compression performance and failure analysis of 3D-printed carbon fiber/PLA composite TPMS lattice structures, *Polymers* 14 (2022), <https://doi.org/10.3390/polym14214595>.
- [74] L.J. Gibson, et al., The mechanics of two-dimensional cellular materials, *Proc. R. Soc. Lond., A. Math. Phys. Sci.* 382 (1782) (1982) 25–42.
- [75] L.J. Gibson, Cellular solids, *Mrs Bull.* 28 (4) (2003) 270–274.
- [76] P. Parandoush, et al., Laser assisted additive manufacturing of continuous fiber reinforced thermoplastic composites, *Mater. Des.* 131 (2017) 186–195.
- [77] P. Pedersen, On optimal orientation of orthotropic materials, *Struct. Optim.* 1 (1989) 101–106.
- [78] H. Gharehbaghi, et al., Residual stiffness and strength analysis of fatigue behavior in a 3D-printed honeycomb structure of continuous glass fiber-reinforced polylactic acid (PLA) composite, *Compos. C: Open Access* 16 (2025) 100552.
- [79] A. Alderson, K. Alderson, *Auxetic materials*. Proceedings of the Institution of Mechanical Engineers, G: J. Aerosp. Eng. 221 (4) (2007) 565–575.
- [80] K.E. Evans, et al., Molecular network design, *Nature* 353 (6340) (1991), 124–124.
- [81] R.S. Lakes, Negative-Poisson's-ratio materials: auxetic solids, *Annu. Rev. Mater. Res.* 47 (1) (2017) 63–81.
- [82] K. Evans, The design of doubly curved sandwich panels with honeycomb cores, *Compos. Struct.* 17 (2) (1991) 95–111.
- [83] K.E. Evans, K. Alderson, Auxetic materials: the positive side of being negative, *Eng. Sci. Educ. J.* 9 (4) (2000) 148–154.
- [84] R. Gatt, et al., On the properties of real finite-sized planar and tubular stent-like auxetic structures, *Phys. Status Solidi (b)* 251 (2) (2014) 321–327.
- [85] F. Amin, et al., Auxetic coronary stent endoprosthesis: fabrication and structural analysis, *J. Appl. Biomater. Funct. Mater.* 13 (2) (2015) 127–135.
- [86] N. Karnesis, G. Burriesci, Uniaxial and buckling mechanical response of auxetic cellular tubes, *Smart Mater. Struct.* 22 (8) (2013) 084008.
- [87] Burriesci, G. and G. Bergamasco, *Annuloplasty prosthesis with an auxetic structure*. 2007.
- [88] P. Mardling, et al., The use of auxetic materials in tissue engineering, *Biomater. Sci.* 8 (8) (2020) 2074–2083.
- [89] P. Ma, et al., Review on the knitted structures with auxetic effect, *J. Text. Inst.* 108 (6) (2017) 947–961.
- [90] K. Alderson, et al., Auxetic warp knit textile structures, *Phys. Status Solidi (b)* 249 (7) (2012) 1322–1329.
- [91] M. Sanami, et al., Auxetic materials for sports applications, *Procedia Eng.* 72 (2014) 453–458.
- [92] A. Alderson, et al., An auxetic filter: a tuneable filter displaying enhanced size selectivity or defouling properties, *Ind. Eng. Chem. Res.* 39 (3) (2000) 654–665.
- [93] A. Forés-Garriga, G. Gómez-Gras, M.A. Pérez, Lightweight hybrid composite sandwich structures with additively manufactured cellular cores, *Thin-Walled Struct.* 191 (2023) 111082.
- [94] S. Song, et al., Fabrication and mechanical behavior of an all-composite interlocked triangular honeycomb sandwich structure: experimental investigation and numerical analysis, *Polym. Compos.* 44 (2) (2023) 833–849.
- [95] Y. He, et al., Pattern transformation of single-material and composite periodic cellular structures, *Mater. Des.* 132 (2017) 375–384.
- [96] H. Veisi, A. Farrokhhabadi, Investigation of the equivalent material properties and failure stress of the re-entrant composite lattice structures using an analytical model, *Compos. Struct.* 257 (2021) 113161.
- [97] A. Farrokhhabadi, et al., Study of equivalent mechanical properties and energy absorption of composite honeycomb structures, *Int. J. Appl. Mech.* 15 (06) (2023) 2350038.
- [98] F. Ghorbani, et al., Investigation of the equivalent mechanical properties of the bone-inspired composite cellular structure: analytical, numerical and experimental approaches, *Compos. Struct.* 309 (2023) 116720.
- [99] A. Farrokhhabadi, M.M. Ashrafi, M. Fotouhi, Design and characterization of an orthotropic accordion cellular honeycomb as one-dimensional morphing structures with enhanced properties, *J. Sandw. Struct. Mater.* 24 (3) (2022) 1726–1745.
- [100] Cui, Z., et al., *3D printed cellular structural composites with continuous fiber reinforcement: a deep study on printing structural parameters and bending performance*. 2022.
- [101] C. Zeng, et al., Temperature-dependent mechanical response of 4D printed composite lattice structures reinforced by continuous fiber, *Compos. Struct.* 280 (2022) 114952.
- [102] B. Liu, et al., Effect of printing path on compressive properties of 3D printed continuous fiber composite negative Poisson's ratio structure, *Polym. Compos.* 44 (10) (2023) 6989–7001.
- [103] X. Zhang, et al., Failure mechanisms and process defects of 3D-printed continuous carbon fiber-reinforced composite cruciform honeycomb structures with different stacking directions, *Aerosp. Sci. Technol.* 148 (2024) 109075.
- [104] P. Cheng, et al., A novel dual-nozzle 3D printing method for continuous fiber reinforced composite cellular structures, *Compos. Commun.* 37 (2023) 101448.
- [105] C. Zeng, et al., Bending performance and failure behavior of 3D printed continuous fiber reinforced composite corrugated sandwich structures with shape memory capability, *Compos. Struct.* 262 (2021) 113626.
- [106] N. Maqsood, M.D. Zaheer, Fabrication of cellular composite structures with continuous fiber reinforcement and different infill patterns using fused filament fabrication, *Addit. Manuf. Front.* 3 (3) (2024) 200156.
- [107] K. Wang, et al., Path planning and bending behaviors of 3D printed continuous carbon fiber reinforced polymer honeycomb structures, *Polymers* 15 (23) (2023) 4485.
- [108] B.-U. Bokharaie, et al., Failure of 3D-printed composite continuous carbon fiber hexagonal frames, *Compos. B: Eng.* 275 (2024) 111307.
- [109] A. Musavi, et al., Investigation of the equivalent mechanical and thermal properties of the kite-shaped fiber-reinforced cellular structure: analytical, numerical and experimental approaches, *Eng. Struct.* 337 (2025) 120517.
- [110] N. Van de Werken, et al., Additively manufactured carbon fiber-reinforced composites: state of the art and perspective, *Addit. Manuf.* 31 (2020) 100962.
- [111] S. Wickramasinghe, T. Do, P. Tran, FDM-based 3D printing of polymer and associated composite: a review on mechanical properties, defects and treatments, *Polymers* 12 (7) (2020) 1529.
- [112] X. He, et al., 3D printing of continuous fiber-reinforced thermoset composites, *Addit. Manuf.* 40 (2021) 101921.
- [113] M. Eichenhofer, J.C. Wong, P. Ermanni, Continuous lattice fabrication of ultra-lightweight composite structures, *Addit. Manuf.* 18 (2017) 48–57.
- [114] Z. Wang, et al., Mechanical and self-monitoring behaviors of 3D printing smart continuous carbon fiber-thermoplastic lattice truss sandwich structure, *Compos. B: Eng.* 176 (2019) 107215.
- [115] D. Zhang, et al., Spatial 3D printing of continuous fiber-reinforced composite multilayer truss structures with controllable structural performance, *Polymers* 15 (21) (2023) 4333.
- [116] J.Y. Jung, et al., Process-structure-property study of 3D-printed continuous fiber reinforced composites, *Compos. A: Appl. Sci. Manuf.* 188 (2025) 108538.
- [117] W. Hao, et al., Preparation and characterization of 3D printed continuous carbon fiber reinforced thermosetting composites, *Polym. Test.* 65 (2018) 29–34.
- [118] A. Sreekumar, S.K. Barman, Physics-informed model order reduction for laminated composites: a Grassmann manifold approach, *Compos. Struct.* 361 (2025) 119035.
- [119] X. Wei, D. Li, J. Xiong, Fabrication and mechanical behaviors of an all-composite sandwich structure with a hexagon honeycomb core based on the tailor-folding approach, *Compos. Sci. Technol.* 184 (2019) 107878.

- [120] H. Rebelo, et al., Experimental and numerical investigation on 3D printed PLA sacrificial honeycomb cladding, *Int. J. Impact Eng.* 131 (2019) 162–173.
- [121] G. Sun, et al., Experimental study on crashworthiness of empty/aluminum foam/honeycomb-filled CFRP tubes, *Compos. Struct.* 152 (2016) 969–993.
- [122] F. Cote, et al., The out-of-plane compressive behavior of metallic honeycombs, *Mater. Sci. Eng.: A* 380 (1–2) (2004) 272–280.
- [123] H. Liu, et al., Flatwise compression property of hierarchical thermoplastic composite square lattice, *Compos. Struct.* 210 (2019) 118–133.
- [124] Z. Wang, et al., Theoretical assessment methodology on axial compressed hexagonal honeycomb's energy absorption capability, *Mech. Adv. Mater. Struct.* 23 (5) (2016) 503–512.
- [125] Y. Zhang, et al., Out-of-plane mechanical behaviors of a side hierarchical honeycomb, *Mech. Mater.* 140 (2020) 103227.
- [126] B. Han, et al., Collapse mechanisms of metallic sandwich structures with aluminum foam-filled corrugated cores, *J. Mech. Mater. Struct.* 9 (4) (2014) 397–425.
- [127] X. Cao, et al., Mechanical properties of an improved 3D-printed rhombic dodecahedron stainless steel lattice structure of variable cross section, *Int. J. Mech. Sci.* 145 (2018) 53–63.
- [128] C. Shu, S. Zhao, S. Hou, Crashworthiness analysis of two-layered corrugated sandwich panels under crushing loading, *Thin-Walled Struct.* 133 (2018) 42–51.
- [129] F. Habib, et al., In-plane energy absorption evaluation of 3D printed polymeric honeycombs, *Virtual Phys. Prototyp.* 12 (2) (2017) 117–131.
- [130] J. Zhang, et al., Quasi-static large deformation compressive behaviour of origami-based metamaterials, *Int. J. Mech. Sci.* 153 (2019) 194–207.
- [131] H.L. Amin Farrokhbadi, X. Yang, A. Rauf, R. Talemi, A.H. Behraves, S. K. Hedayati, D. Chronopoulos, Energy absorption assessment of recovered shapes in 3D-printed star hourglass honeycombs: experimental and numerical approaches, *Compos. Struct.* 347 (2024) 118444.
- [132] F.C. Smith, F.L. Scarpa, G. Burriesci, Simultaneous optimization of the electromagnetic and mechanical properties of honeycomb materials. *Smart Structures and Materials 2002: Smart Structures and Integrated Systems*, SPIE, 2002.
- [133] W. Zhang, et al., Characterization of residual stress and deformation in additively manufactured ABS polymer and composite specimens, *Compos. Sci. Technol.* 150 (2017) 102–110.
- [134] G. Wang, et al., A new path planning strategy driven by geometric features and tensile properties for 3D printing of continuous fiber reinforced thermoplastic composites, *Compos. B: Eng.* 288 (2025) 111885.
- [135] P. Qu, et al., Additive manufacturing of hybrid continuous carbon/basalt fiber reinforced composites based on bi-matrix co-extrusion, *J. Mater. Res. Technol.* 30 (2024) 8683–8704.
- [136] H. Wu, et al., Nacre-like carbon fiber-reinforced biomimetic ceramic composites: fabrication, microstructure, and mechanical performance, *Ceram. Int.* 50 (14) (2024) 25388–25399.
- [137] H.-J. Um, et al., Mechanical performance of novel curved sandwich structures featuring 3D printed continuous carbon fiber/polyamide 6 composite corrugated core with rail interlocking, *Compos. B: Eng.* 295 (2025) 112222.
- [138] S. David Müzel, et al., Application of the finite element method in the analysis of composite materials: a review, *Polymers* 12 (2020), <https://doi.org/10.3390/polym12040818>.
- [139] A. Farrokhbadi, et al., Assessment of fiber-reinforcement and foam-filling in the directional energy absorption performance of a 3D printed accordion cellular structure, *Compos. Struct.* 297 (2022) 115945.
- [140] X. Li, et al., Multi-scale numerical analysis of damage modes in 3D stitched composites, *Int. J. Mech. Sci.* 266 (2024) 108983.
- [141] X.-T. Wang, Y.-L. Chen, L. Ma, The manufacture and characterization of composite three-dimensional re-entrant auxetic cellular structures made from carbon fiber reinforced polymer, *J. Compos. Mater.* 52 (23) (2018) 3265–3273.
- [142] Z.-Y. Li, et al., Multifunctional acoustic and mechanical metamaterials prepared from continuous CFRP composites, *Mater. Horiz.* 12 (2) (2025) 458–472.
- [143] Y. Wang, H. Xu, D. Pasini, Multiscale isogeometric topology optimization for lattice materials, *Comput. Methods Appl. Mech. Eng.* 316 (2017) 568–585.
- [144] Y. Lu, L. Tong, Concurrent topology optimization of cellular structures and anisotropic materials, *Comput. Struct.* 255 (2021) 106624.
- [145] Z. Shu, L. Gao, H. Li, A multivariate level set method for concurrent optimization of graded lattice structures with multiple microstructure prototypes, *Comput. Methods Appl. Mech. Eng.* 425 (2024) 116962.
- [146] A. Sreekumar, L. Zhong, D. Chronopoulos, A novel empirical interpolation surrogate for digital twin wave-based structural health monitoring with MATLAB implementation, *Mathematics* 13 (2025), <https://doi.org/10.3390/math13111730>.
- [147] Y. Tang, A. Kurtz, Y.F. Zhao, Bidirectional Evolutionary Structural Optimization (BESO) based design method for lattice structure to be fabricated by additive manufacturing, *Comput. Aided Des. (C)* 69 (2015) 91–101.
- [148] Ju, J., et al., *Experiment and simulation study on the crashworthiness of markforged 3D-printed carbon/kevlar hybrid continuous fiber composite honeycomb structures. LID - 10.3390/ma18010192 [doi] LID - 192. (1996-1944 (Print))*.
- [149] S. Lee, et al., Multi-scale design of composite material structures for maximizing fundamental natural frequency, *Comput. Methods Appl. Mech. Eng.* 425 (2024) 116928.
- [150] O. Abdeljaber, O. Avci, D.J. Inman, Optimization of chiral lattice based metastructures for broadband vibration suppression using genetic algorithms, *J. Sound Vib.* 369 (2016) 50–62.
- [151] L. Wang, Y. Cai, D. Liu, Multiscale reliability-based topology optimization methodology for truss-like microstructures with unknown-but-bounded uncertainties, *Comput. Methods Appl. Mech. Eng.* 339 (2018) 358–388.
- [152] Y. Tang, A. Kurtz, Y.F. Zhao, Bidirectional evolutionary structural optimization (BESO) based design method for lattice structure to be fabricated by additive manufacturing, *Comput.-Aided Des.* 69 (2015) 91–101.
- [153] N. Boddeti, et al., Optimal design and manufacture of variable stiffness laminated continuous fiber reinforced composites, *Sci. Rep.* 10 (1) (2020) 16507.
- [154] J. Lee, et al., Topology optimization for continuous and discrete orientation design of functionally graded fiber-reinforced composite structures, *Compos. Struct.* 201 (2018) 217–233.
- [155] H. Zhang, et al., 3D printing of continuous carbon fibre reinforced polymer composites with optimised structural topology and fibre orientation, *Compos. Struct.* 313 (2023) 116914.
- [156] V.T. Ramamoorthy, et al., Comparison of heuristics and metaheuristics for topology optimisation in acoustic porous materials, *J. Acoust. Soc. Am.* 150 (4) (2021) 3164–3175.
- [157] V.-N. Hoang, et al., Design of lattice structures with direct multiscale topology optimization, *Compos. Struct.* 252 (2020) 112718.
- [158] Y. Zhang, L. Gao, M. Xiao, Maximizing natural frequencies of inhomogeneous cellular structures by Kriging-assisted multiscale topology optimization, *Comput. Struct.* 230 (2020) 106197.
- [159] M. Abu-Mualla, J. Huang, Inverse design of 3D cellular materials with physics-guided machine learning, *Mater. Des.* 232 (2023) 112103.
- [160] V. Gupta, A. Kidane, Designing density-graded cellular materials for tailored constitutive response, *Compos. B: Eng.* 287 (2024) 111793.
- [161] J. Zhang, Q. An, Topology optimization of fibre reinforced polymer lattice structures for additive manufacturing, *Compos. Sci. Technol.* 242 (2023) 110144.
- [162] N. Rahmat, J. Kadkhodapour, M. Arbabtafi, Mechanical characterization of additively manufactured orthopedic cellular implants: case study on different cell types and effect of defects, *Phys. Mesomech.* 26 (4) (2023) 443–458.
- [163] H. Gonabadi, et al., Size effects of voids on the mechanical properties of 3D printed parts, *Int. J. Adv. Manuf. Technol.* 132 (11) (2024) 5439–5456.
- [164] L. Cheng, et al., Efficient design optimization of variable-density cellular structures for additive manufacturing: theory and experimental validation, *Rapid Prototyp. J.* 23 (4) (2017) 660–677.
- [165] S.S. Esfahlani, et al., Hexagonal honeycomb cell optimisation by way of meta-model techniques, *Int. J. Crashworthiness* 18 (3) (2013) 264–275.
- [166] H. Li, et al., Integrated design of cellular composites using a level-set topology optimization method, *Comput. Methods Appl. Mech. Eng.* 309 (2016) 453–475.
- [167] C. Qi, F. Jiang, S. Yang, Advanced honeycomb designs for improving mechanical properties: a review, *Compos. B: Eng.* 227 (2021) 109393.
- [168] V.-N. Hoang, et al., Adaptive concurrent topology optimization of cellular composites for additive manufacturing, *JOM* 72 (6) (2020) 2378–2390.
- [169] J. Gao, et al., Dynamic multiscale topology optimization for multi-regional micro-structured cellular composites, *Compos. Struct.* 211 (2019) 401–417.
- [170] Y. Zhang, et al., Multiscale topology optimization for minimizing frequency responses of cellular composites with connectable graded microstructures, *Mech. Syst. Signal Process.* 135 (2020) 106369.
- [171] A. Radman, X. Huang, Y.M. Xie, Topological optimization for the design of microstructures of isotropic cellular materials, *Eng. Optim.* 45 (11) (2013) 1331–1348.
- [172] V.S. Papapetrou, C. Patel, A.Y. Tamijani, Stiffness-based optimization framework for the topology and fiber paths of continuous fiber composites, *Compos. B: Eng.* 183 (2020) 107681.
- [173] B. Fedulov, et al., Optimization of parts manufactured using continuous fiber three-dimensional printing technology, *Compos. B: Eng.* 227 (2021) 109406.
- [174] Y. Gandhi, G. Minak, A review on topology optimization strategies for additively manufactured continuous fiber-reinforced composite structures, *Appl. Sci.* 12 (2022), <https://doi.org/10.3390/app12211211>.
- [175] S. Velumani, P. Navaneetha Krishnan, S. Jayabal, Mathematical modeling and optimization of mechanical properties of short coir fiber-reinforced vinyl ester composite using genetic algorithm method, *Mech. Adv. Mater. Struct.* 21 (7) (2014) 559–565.
- [176] X. Ma, et al., Concurrent multi-scale optimization of hybrid composite plates and shells for vibration, *Compos. Struct.* 233 (2020) 111635.
- [177] H. Li, et al., Topology optimization for functionally graded cellular composites with metamaterials by level sets, *Comput. Methods Appl. Mech. Eng.* 328 (2018) 340–364.
- [178] J. Zheng, et al., Robust topology optimization for cellular composites with hybrid uncertainties, *Int. J. Numer. Methods Eng.* 115 (6) (2018) 695–713.
- [179] L. Wang, et al., Data-driven multiscale design of cellular composites with multiclass microstructures for natural frequency maximization, *Compos. Struct.* 280 (2022) 114949.
- [180] Y. Huang, et al., Multiscale concurrent design and 3D printing of continuous fiber reinforced thermoplastic composites with optimized fiber trajectory and topological structure, *Compos. Struct.* 285 (2022) 115241.
- [181] Z. Duan, et al., Concurrent multi-material and multi-scale design optimization of fiber-reinforced composite material and structures for minimum structural compliance, *Compos. Struct.* 311 (2023) 116796.
- [182] J. Yan, et al., Concurrent multi-scale design optimization of composite frame structures using the Heaviside penalization of discrete material model, *Acta Mech. Sin.* 32 (3) (2016) 430–441.
- [183] X. Su, W. Chen, S. Liu, Multi-scale topology optimization for minimizing structural compliance of cellular composites with connectable graded microstructures, *Struct. Multidiscip. Optim.* 64 (4) (2021) 2609–2625.

- [184] W. Zhu, et al., Simulation analysis and optimization of 3D printed continuous carbon fiber reinforced composites, *Compos. Struct.* 355 (2025) 118840.
- [185] S. Huo, et al., Thermal design of functionally graded cellular structures with multiple microstructure configurations through topology optimization, *Compos. Struct.* 313 (2023) 116922.
- [186] C. Oztan, et al., Microstructure and mechanical properties of three dimensional-printed continuous fiber composites, *J. Compos. Mater.* 53 (2) (2018) 271–280.
- [187] S. Huang, et al., Characterization of interfacial properties between fibre and polymer matrix in composite materials – A critical review, *J. Mater. Res. Technol.* 13 (2021) 1441–1484.
- [188] F. Liu, et al., Mechanical and interfacial analysis of 3D-printed two-matrix continuous carbon fibre composites for enhanced structural performance, *Compos. A: Appl. Sci. Manuf.* 180 (2024) 108105.
- [189] D. Calnerytė, et al., Multi-scale finite element modeling of 3D printed structures subjected to mechanical loads, *Rapid Prototyp. J.* 24 (2017), 00–00.
- [190] E. Monaldo, S. Marfia, Multiscale technique for the analysis of 3D-printed materials, *Int. J. Solids Struct.* 232 (2021) 111173.
- [191] M. Spahic, et al., Multi-scale analysis of the flexural behaviour of 3D printed cellular polymer materials: comparison between morphing and sandwich beams, *Compos. Struct.* 273 (2021) 114249.
- [192] J. Zhang, W. Yang, Y. Li, Process-dependent multiscale modeling for 3D printing of continuous fibre-reinforced composites, *Addit. Manuf.* 73 (2023) 103680.
- [193] H. Zhang, J. Chen, D. Yang, Fibre misalignment and breakage in 3D printing of continuous carbon fibre reinforced thermoplastic composites, *Addit. Manuf.* 38 (2021) 101775.
- [194] Rastogi, P., S. Gharde, and B. Kandasubramanian, *Thermal effects in 3D printed parts*, in *3D printing in biomedical engineering*, S. Singh, C. Prakash, and R. Singh, Eds. 2020, Springer Singapore: Singapore. p. 43–68.
- [195] A.Y. Al-Maharma, S.P. Patil, B. Markert, Effects of porosity on the mechanical properties of additively manufactured components: a critical review, *Mater. Res. Express* 7 (12) (2020) 122001.
- [196] M. Rimašauskas, et al., Investigation of influence of printing parameters on the quality of 3D printed composite structures, *Compos. Struct.* 281 (2022) 115061.
- [197] Y. Tao, et al., A review on voids of 3D printed parts by fused filament fabrication, *J. Mater. Res. Technol.* 15 (2021) 4860–4879.
- [198] P. Tran, et al., Bimaterial 3D printing and numerical analysis of bio-inspired composite structures under in-plane and transverse loadings, *Compos. B: Eng.* 108 (2017) 210–223.
- [199] S. Yuan, et al., Additive manufacturing of polymeric composites from material processing to structural design, *Compos. B: Eng.* 219 (2021) 108903.
- [200] H. Lu, et al., Uncertainty quantification for damage detection in 3D-printed auxetic structures using ultrasonic guided waves and a probabilistic neural network, *Thin-Walled Struct.* 205 (2024) 112466.
- [201] F. Bartl, et al., Material behaviour of a cellular composite undergoing large deformations, *Int. J. Impact Eng.* 36 (5) (2009) 667–679.
- [202] L.A. Mihai, A. Goriely, Finite deformation effects in cellular structures with hyperelastic cell walls, *Int. J. Solids Struct.* 53 (2015) 107–128.
- [203] C. Peng, P. Tran, A.P. Mouritz, Compression and buckling analysis of 3D printed carbon fibre-reinforced polymer cellular composite structures, *Compos. Struct.* 300 (2022) 116167.
- [204] M. Alfouneh, B. Keshtegar, The topology optimization of cellular or multi-material composite structures under dynamic loading, *J. Braz. Soc. Mech. Sci. Eng.* 45 (4) (2023) 206.
- [205] J. Gan, et al., Dynamic failure of 3D printed negative-stiffness meta-sandwich structures under repeated impact loadings, *Compos. Sci. Technol.* 234 (2023) 109928.
- [206] J. Zhong, et al., Mechanical behaviors of composite auxetic structures under quasi-static compression and dynamic impact, *Eur. J. Mech. - A/Solids* 109 (2025) 105454.
- [207] R. Burguño, et al., Load-bearing natural fiber composite cellular beams and panels, *Compos. A: Appl. Sci. Manuf.* 35 (6) (2004) 645–656.
- [208] Z. Hu, et al., Design of ultra-lightweight and high-strength cellular structural composites inspired by biomimetics, *Compos. B: Eng.* 121 (2017) 108–121.
- [209] M.R. Khosravani, et al., Structural performance of 3D-printed composites under various loads and environmental conditions, *Polym. Test.* 91 (2020) 106770.
- [210] H. Yin, et al., Crushing analysis and optimization for bio-inspired hierarchical 3D cellular structure, *Compos. Struct.* 286 (2022) 115333.
- [211] M.I. Okereke, A.I. Akpoyomare, M.S. Bingley, Virtual testing of advanced composites, cellular materials and biomaterials: a review, *Compos. B: Eng.* 60 (2014) 637–662.
- [212] A. Uşun, R. Gümrük, The mechanical performance of the 3D printed composites produced with continuous carbon fiber reinforced filaments obtained via melt impregnation, *Addit. Manuf.* 46 (2021) 102112.
- [213] M. Kuczewicz, et al., Modelling, and characterization of 3D printed cellular structures, *Mater. Des.* 142 (2018) 177–189.
- [214] I.M. Alarifi, Revolutionising fabrication advances and applications of 3D printing with composite materials: a review, *Virtual Phys. Prototyp.* 19 (1) (2024) e2390504.
- [215] T. Fruleux, et al., Geometric limitations of 3D printed continuous flax-fiber reinforced biocomposites cellular lattice structures, *Compos. C: Open Access* 9 (2022) 100313.
- [216] G. Ma, et al., Mechanical anisotropy of aligned fiber reinforced composite for extrusion-based 3D printing, *Constr. Build. Mater.* 202 (2019) 770–783.
- [217] A. Nazir, et al., Multi-material additive manufacturing: A systematic review of design, properties, applications, challenges, and 3D printing of materials and cellular metamaterials, *Mater. Des.* 226 (2023) 111661.
- [218] T.D. Ngo, et al., Additive manufacturing (3D printing): A review of materials, methods, applications and challenges, *Compos. B: Eng.* 143 (2018) 172–196.
- [219] J. Sario, et al., A review on 3D printed matrix polymer composites: its potential and future challenges, *Int. J. Adv. Manuf. Technol.* 106 (5) (2020) 1695–1721.
- [220] S.M.F. Kabir, K. Mathur, A.-F.M. Seyam, A critical review on 3D printed continuous fiber-reinforced composites: History, mechanism, materials and properties, *Compos. Struct.* 232 (2020) 111476.
- [221] M.S. Irfan, et al., Thermal and morphological analysis of various 3D printed composite honeycomb cores, *Compos. Struct.* 290 (2022) 115517.
- [222] X. Huang, H. Tang, L. Wang, Effect of residual stress on mechanical properties of Triply periodic minimal surface lattice structures in additive manufacturing, *Comput. Mater. Sci.* 245 (2024) 113318.
- [223] J. Thomas, et al., Graded cellular structures for enhanced performance of additively manufactured orthopaedic implants, *Int. J. Adv. Manuf. Technol.* 130 (3) (2024) 1887–1900.
- [224] A. Arefi, A. Sreekumar, D. Chronopoulos, A programmable hybrid energy harvester: leveraging buckling and magnetic multistability, *Micromachines* 16 (2025), <https://doi.org/10.3390/mi16040359>.
- [225] J. Lv, et al., Two-scale topology optimization of the 3D plant-inspired adaptive cellular structures for morphing applications, *J. Aerosp. Eng.* 33 (4) (2020) 04020032.
- [226] J. Wang, et al., Finite element modeling of the damping capacity and vibration behavior of cellular shape memory alloy, *Mech. Adv. Mater. Struct.* 29 (15) (2022) 2142–2155.
- [227] P. Eghbali, et al., Study in circular auxetic structures for efficiency enhancement in piezoelectric vibration energy harvesting, *Sci. Rep.* 10 (1) (2020) 16338.
- [228] J. Joy, et al., Chapter 17 - Applications of self-healing polymeric systems, in: S. Thomas, A. Surendran (Eds.), *Self-Healing Polymer-Based Systems*, Elsevier, 2020, pp. 495–513.
- [229] N. Top, H. Gökçe, I. Şahin, Additive manufacturing of bio-inspired microstructures for bone tissue engineering, *Exp. Tech.* 47 (6) (2023) 1213–1227.
- [230] A. Singh, B. Koohbor, G. Youssef, Full-field characterizations of additively manufactured composite cellular structures, *Compos. B: Eng.* 272 (2024) 111208.
- [231] P. Singh, et al., Green materials and India: a bibliometric analysis, *Mater. Today: Proc.* (2023).
- [232] L. Zhang, et al., Epoxy resin-hydrated halt shaped composite thermal control packaging material for thermal management of electronic components, *J. Clean. Prod.* 363 (2022) 132369.
- [233] L. Viti, M.S. Vitiello, Tailored nano-electronics and photonics with two-dimensional materials at terahertz frequencies, *J. Appl. Phys.* 130 (17) (2021) 170903.
- [234] I. Chiesa, et al., 4D printing shape-morphing hybrid biomaterials for advanced bioengineering applications, *Materials* 16 (2023), <https://doi.org/10.3390/ma16206661>.
- [235] W. Wu, et al., Mechanostructures: rational mechanical design, fabrication, performance evaluation, and industrial application of advanced structures, *Prog. Mater. Sci.* 131 (2023) 101021.
- [236] J. Kos, et al., Improving sustainability of additive manufacturing processes based on digital twins – a case study, *Proc. Des. Soc.* 4 (2024) 2089–2098.
- [237] A. Mardanshahi, et al., Sensing techniques for structural health monitoring: a state-of-the-art review on performance criteria and new-generation technologies, *Sensors* 25 (2025), <https://doi.org/10.3390/s25051424>.
- [238] M.J. Prajapati, et al., Multi-material additive manufacturing with lightweight closed-cell foam-filled lattice structures for enhanced mechanical and functional properties, *Addit. Manuf.* 54 (2022) 102766.
- [239] C.L.C. Chan, J.M. Taylor, E.C. Davidson, Design of soft matter for additive processing, *Nat. Synth.* 1 (8) (2022) 592–600.
- [240] C. Zeng, et al., Mechanical properties and shape memory behavior of 4D printed functionally graded cellular structures, *Sci. China Technol. Sci.* 66 (12) (2023) 3522–3533.
- [241] A. Casalotti, F. D’Annibale, G. Rosi, Optimization of an architected composite with tailored graded properties, *Z. angew. Math. Phys.* 75 (4) (2024) 126.
- [242] Z. Li, et al., Inverse design of cellular structures with the geometry of triply periodic minimal surfaces using generative artificial intelligence algorithms, *Eng. Struct.* 321 (2024) 118988.
- [243] Y. Bai, et al., Unique cellular microstructure-enabled hybrid additive and subtractive manufacturing of aluminium alloy mirror with high strength, *J. Mater. Process. Technol.* 320 (2023) 118095.
- [244] M.J. Prajapati, A. Kumar, J.-Y. Jeng, Additive manufacturing of liquid-entrapped architected structures, *Adv. Mater. Technol.* n/a (n/a) (2025) e00446.
- [245] M.H. Zubayer, et al., Enhancing additive manufacturing precision: intelligent inspection and optimization for defect-free continuous carbon fiber-reinforced polymer, *Compos. C: Open Access* 14 (2024) 100451.
- [246] O. Bliyah, et al., 3D printing stretchable and compressible porous structures by polymerizable emulsions for soft robotics, *Mater. Horiz.* 10 (11) (2023) 4976–4985.
- [247] L. Ferrari, et al., Sandwich structured ceramic matrix composites with periodic cellular ceramic cores: an active cooled thermal protection for space vehicles, *Compos. Struct.* 154 (2016) 61–68.
- [248] A.L. Avila-Marin, et al., Experimental study of innovative periodic cellular structures as air volumetric absorbers, *Renew. Energy* 184 (2022) 391–404.
- [249] A.H. Alami, et al., Progress in 3D printing in wind energy and its role in achieving sustainability, *Int. J. Thermofluids* 20 (2023) 100496.
- [250] W. Liu, et al., Theoretical, numerical and experimental study on the in-plane elastic behavior of a 2D chiral cellular structure, *Compos. Struct.* 296 (2022) 115889.

- [251] P. Kaczyński, M. Ptak, K. Gawdzińska, Energy absorption of cast metal and composite foams tested in extremely low and high-temperatures, *Mater. Des.* 196 (2021) 109114.
- [252] Z. Sági, R. Butler, Properties of cryogenic and low temperature composite materials – a review, *Cryogenics* 111 (2020) 103190.
- [253] P. Wanchoo, et al., Investigations on air and underwater blast mitigation in polymeric composite structures – a review, *Compos. Struct.* 263 (2021) 113530.
- [254] D.K. Gara, et al., 4D bioprinting: a review on smart bio-adaptable technology to print stimuli-responsive materials, *Prog. Addit. Manuf.* (2024).
- [255] M. Ulbin, et al., Computational fatigue analysis of auxetic cellular structures made of SLM AlSi10Mg alloy, *Metals* 10 (2020), <https://doi.org/10.3390/met10070945>.
- [256] A. Hussain, et al., Sustainable fabrication of polypropylene-postconsumer cotton composite materials: circularity, characterization, mechanical testing, and tribology, *Mater. Today Sustain.* 22 (2023) 100344.
- [257] A.E. Krauklis, et al., Composite material recycling technology—state-of-the-art and sustainable development for the 2020s, *J. Compos. Sci.* 5 (2021), <https://doi.org/10.3390/jcs5010028>.
- [258] Z. Chai, M. Fang, X. Min, Composite phase-change materials for photo-thermal conversion and energy storage: a review, *Nano Energy* 124 (2024) 109437.
- [259] G. Karalis, et al., Advanced glass fiber polymer composite laminate operating as a thermoelectric generator: a structural device for micropower generation and potential large-scale thermal energy harvesting, *ACS Appl. Mater. Interfaces* 13 (20) (2021) 24138–24153.
- [260] M.A. Sari, et al., High performance Ca₃-xAg_{0.3}LaxCo₄O₉ materials for aerospace applications of thermoelectric devices, *J. Mater. Sci. Mater. Electron.* 35 (24) (2024) 1640.
- [261] Y. Li, et al., Cryogenic thermal conductivity of carbon fiber reinforced polymer composite laminates, *Int. J. Heat Mass Transf.* 226 (2024) 125521.
- [262] S. Pawlak, et al., Measurement of the anisotropic thermal conductivity of carbon-fiber/epoxy composites based on laser-induced temperature field: Experimental investigation and numerical analysis, *Int. Commun. Heat Mass Transf.* 139 (2022) 106401.
- [263] J. Wu, et al., Thermal control of polarization of light with nonlocal plasmonic anisotropic metamaterials, *Appl. Phys. Lett.* 123 (17) (2023) 171701.
- [264] S. Ganeshkumar, et al., Exploring the potential of nano technology: a assessment of nano-scale multi-layered-composite coatings for cutting tool performance, *Arab. J. Chem.* 16 (10) (2023) 105173.
- [265] E. Mermer, R. Ünal, Passive thermal control systems in spacecrafts, *J. Braz. Soc. Mech. Sci. Eng.* 45 (3) (2023) 160.
- [266] M. Ahmad, A. Nighojkar, A. Plappally, A review of the methods of harvesting atmospheric moisture, *Environ. Sci. Pollut. Res.* 31 (7) (2024) 10395–10416.
- [267] H. Yue, et al., Fog collection behavior of bionic surface and large fog collector: a review, *Adv. Colloid Interface Sci.* 300 (2022) 102583.
- [268] K. Chen, et al., Facile fabrication of transparent slippery coatings with dual self-healing ability, *Appl. Surf. Sci.* 639 (2023) 158207.
- [269] P. Gao, et al., Vibration analysis and control technologies of hydraulic pipeline system in aircraft: a review, *Chin. J. Aeronaut.* 34 (4) (2021) 83–114.
- [270] D. Hong, H. Moon, B. Kim, Bidirectional active vibration control of two-dimensional structure inspired by automotive engine mounting system, *J. Mech. Sci. Technol.* 38 (5) (2024) 2231–2246.
- [271] B. Wang, et al., Test and analysis of multi-cavity particle damper for vertical vibration control of pipeline structures, *Eng. Struct.* 281 (2023) 115744.
- [272] H. Zhang, et al., Numerical and experimental investigation of an auxetic piezoelectric energy harvester with frequency self-tuning capability, *Smart Mater. Struct.* 33 (5) (2024) 055022.
- [273] D.D. Singh, et al., Design and analysis of vibration fixture for aerospace heat exchanger, *J. Vib. Eng. Technol.* 12 (4) (2024) 5609–5624.
- [274] Z. Shu, R. You, Y. Zhou, Viscoelastic materials for structural dampers: a review, *Constr. Build. Mater.* 342 (2022) 127955.
- [275] U. Arasan, et al., Condensed finite element scheme for symmetric multi-layer structures including dilatational motion, *J. Sound Vib.* 536 (2022) 117105.
- [276] A. Sreekumar, I.A. Kougoumtzoglou, S.P. Triantafyllou, Filter approximations for random vibroacoustics of rigid porous media, *ASCE-ASME J Risk Uncert Engrg Sys B Mech Engrg* 10 (3) (2024).
- [277] A. Ahmed, et al., 4D printing: fundamentals, materials, applications and challenges, *Polymer* 228 (2021) 123926.
- [278] M.J. Carvajal Loaiza, O.I. Ojeda, V. Restrepo, Adaptive bioinspired morphing surface using temperature-responsive elastomer-SMA composites, *Extreme Mech. Lett.* 72 (2024) 102235.
- [279] J. Wong, et al., Mechano-activated objects with multidirectional shape morphing programmed via 3D printing, *ACS Appl. Polym. Mater.* 2 (7) (2020) 2504–2508.
- [280] M. Khezri, K.J.R. Rasmussen, Functionalising buckling for structural morphing in kinetic façades: concepts, strategies and applications, *Thin-Walled Struct.* 180 (2022) 109749.
- [281] D. Ahmad, et al., Recent developments of polymer-based skins for morphing wing applications, *Polym. Test.* 135 (2024) 108463.
- [282] A. Bhat, et al., Review on nanocomposites based on aerospace applications, *Nanotechnol. Rev.* 10 (1) (2021) 237–253.
- [283] A. Airoidi, et al., Design of a morphing airfoil with composite chiral structure, *J. Aircr.* 49 (4) (2012) 1008–1019.
- [284] S. Jacobs, et al., Deployable auxetic shape memory alloy cellular antenna demonstrator: design, manufacturing and modal testing, *Smart Mater. Struct.* 21 (7) (2012) 075013.
- [285] M. Kulkarni, H. Nguyen, K. Alexis, The reconfigurable aerial robotic chain: shape and motion planning, *IFAC-Pap.* 53 (2) (2020) 9295–9302.
- [286] Y. Xu, et al., Tunable mechanical behavior of auxetic cementitious cellular composites (CCCs): experiments and simulations, *Constr. Build. Mater.* 266 (2021) 121388.
- [287] Z. Li, K.D. Tsavdaridis, L. Gardner, *A Review of Optimised Additively Manufactured Steel Connections for Modular Building Systems*, in *Industrializing Additive Manufacturing*, Springer International Publishing, Cham, 2021.
- [288] A. Sreekumar, S.P. Triantafyllou, F. Chevillotte, Virtual elements for sound propagation in complex poroelastic media, *Comput. Mech.* 69 (1) (2022) 347–382.
- [289] F.P.V. Ferreira, C.H. Martins, S. De Nardin, Advances in composite beams with web openings and composite cellular beams, *J. Constr. Steel Res.* 172 (2020) 106182.
- [290] A. Sreekumar, et al., Resolving vibro-acoustics in poroelastic media via a multiscale virtual element method, *Int. J. Numer. Methods Eng.* 124 (7) (2023) 1510–1546.
- [291] X. Hou, B. Wang, Z. Deng, Tailored energy absorption for a novel auxetic honeycomb structure under large deformation, *Sci. China Phys. Mech. Astron.* 67 (5) (2024) 254611.
- [292] A. Corvi, L. Collini, Shear-thickening-fluid-based meta-material for adaptive impact response, *Mater. Des.* 244 (2024) 113174.
- [293] N.K. Choudhry, B. Panda, S. Kumar, Enhanced energy absorption performance of 3D printed 2D auxetic lattices, *Thin-Walled Struct.* 186 (2023) 110650.
- [294] S. Hasanov, et al., Review on additive manufacturing of multi-material parts: progress and challenges, *J. Manuf. Mater. Process.* 6 (2022), <https://doi.org/10.3390/jmmp6010004>.
- [295] H. Mohammadi, et al., An insight from nature: honeycomb pattern in advanced structural design for impact energy absorption, *J. Mater. Res. Technol.* 22 (2023) 2862–2887.
- [296] K.M. Abate, et al., Design, optimization, and validation of mechanical properties of different cellular structures for biomedical application, *Int. J. Adv. Manuf. Technol.* 106 (3) (2020) 1253–1265.
- [297] X. Zhao, et al., Upcycling of waste epoxy thermosets to robust polyurethane foams via an in situ degradation-foaming process, *J. Environ. Chem. Eng.* 11 (2) (2023) 109363.
- [298] M.E. Imanian, et al., 3D printed flexible wearable sensors based on triply periodic minimal surface structures for biomonitoring applications, *Smart Mater. Struct.* 32 (1) (2023) 015015.
- [299] A. Nag, S.C. Mukhopadhyay, The fabrication of printed flexible sensors: challenges and possible outcomes. *Printed and Flexible Sensor Technology*, IOP Publishing, 2021, p. 3–1–3–24.
- [300] H. Salehi, et al., A comprehensive review of self-powered sensors in civil infrastructure: State-of-the-art and future research trends, *Eng. Struct.* 234 (2021) 111963.
- [301] J. Xie, et al., Auxetic cementitious cellular composite (ACCC) PVDF-based energy harvester, *Energy Build.* 298 (2023) 113582.
- [302] J. Meng, et al., The integration of triboelectric nanogenerators and supercapacitors: the key role of cellular materials, *Materials* 16 (2023), <https://doi.org/10.3390/ma16103751>.
- [303] D. Zhang, et al., Lattice architectures for thermoelectric energy harvesting, *ACS Energy Lett.* 9 (5) (2024) 2240–2247.
- [304] L. Wu, et al., A brief review of dynamic mechanical metamaterials for mechanical energy manipulation, *Mater. Today* 44 (2021) 168–193.
- [305] M. Anic, et al., The review of materials for energy harvesting, in: 2021 IEEE 21st International Conference on Bioinformatics and Bioengineering (BIBE), 2021.
- [306] D. Sundeep, E.K. Varadharaj, C.C. Sastry, et al., Effect of interfacial bonding characteristics on electrical properties of natural fiber reinforced polymeric matrixcomposite, in: S. Krishnasamy, et al. (Eds.), *Interfacial Bonding Characteristics in Natural Fiber Reinforced Polymer Composites: Fiber-matrix Interface In Biocomposites*, Springer Nature Singapore, Singapore, 2024, pp. 259–290.
- [307] R. Annie Sujatha, et al., Metal and metal oxide enabled sensors for biomedical applications, in: S. Garg, A. Chandra, S. Sagadevan (Eds.), *Emerging Sustainable Nanomaterials for Biomedical Applications*, Springer Nature Switzerland, Cham, 2024, pp. 187–222.
- [308] S. Chen, et al., Microcellular foamed bilayer IPP/CNTs-HDPE/CNTs nanocomposites for electromagnetic interference shielding application, *J. Polym. Res.* 31 (12) (2024) 357.
- [309] L. Feng, et al., Development of light cellular carbon nanotube@graphene/carbon nanocomposites with effective mechanical and EMI shielding performance, *Carbon* 168 (2020) 719–731.
- [310] Y. Liu, Y. Liu, X. Zhao, MXene composite electromagnetic shielding materials: the latest research status, *ACS Appl. Mater. Interfaces* 16 (31) (2024) 41596–41615.
- [311] J.T. Orasugh, S.S. Ray, Functional and structural facts of effective electromagnetic interference shielding materials: a review, *ACS Omega* 8 (9) (2023) 8134–8158.
- [312] Z. Sun, et al., Foam materials for applications of electromagnetic shielding and microwave absorption, *Mater. Res. Bull.* 180 (2024) 113001.
- [313] B. Zhao, et al., Advances in electromagnetic shielding properties of composite foams, *J. Mater. Chem. A* 9 (14) (2021) 8896–8949.
- [314] S. Li, et al., Constructing honeycomb-like hierarchical foam via electromagnetic cooperation strategy for broadband microwave absorption, *Carbon* 215 (2023) 118425.
- [315] S.-j. Yang, et al., A review of the use of graphene-based materials in electromagnetic-shielding, *New Carbon Mater.* 39 (2) (2024) 223–239.
- [316] J. Wu, Y. Gao, High-performance electromagnetic shielding composite materials based on carbon nanotubes and Sandwich laminate structures, *Polym. Compos.* 45 (15) (2024) 13639–13649.

- [317] Y. Hu, et al., Chapter 14 - Metallic nanocomposite foams for electromagnetic interference shielding, in: S. Thomas, C. Paoloni, A.R. Pai (Eds.), *Porous Nanocomposites for Electromagnetic Interference Shielding*, Woodhead Publishing, 2024, pp. 315–336.
- [318] D. Huang, et al., Graphite nanosheet-based carbon foams for electromagnetic interference shielding, *ACS Appl. Nano Mater.* 5 (11) (2022) 16784–16792.
- [319] A.A. Isari, et al., Structural design for EMI shielding: from underlying mechanisms to common pitfalls, *Adv. Mater.* 36 (24) (2024) 2310683.
- [320] B. Zhao, et al., Dependence of electromagnetic interference shielding ability of conductive polymer composite foams with hydrophobic properties on cellular structure, *J. Mater. Chem. C* 8 (22) (2020) 7401–7410.
- [321] L. Omana, et al., Recent advances in polymer nanocomposites for electromagnetic interference shielding: a review, *ACS Omega* 7 (30) (2022) 25921–25947.